

Mode of Action of nano Titanium Dioxide in Combination with Cadmium when exposed to Simulated Solar Radiation

Thesis

submitted in partial fulfilment

of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy

School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences

at the

University of the West of Scotland

in collaboration with the

Hamburg University of Applied Sciences

by

Lisa Taplick

ID No: B00339746

September 2023

Advisors Prof. Dr. Susanne Heise

Prof. Dr. Andrew S. Hursthouse

Contents

Acknowledgements	VI
Statutory Declaration	VIII
Summary.....	IX
Index of Symbols and Abbreviations	XI
1 Introduction.....	1
2 State of the Art.....	3
2.1 Titanium dioxide nanoparticles	3
2.1.1 Crystal structure	3
2.1.2 Photocatalytic activity	5
2.1.3 Primary particles and agglomeration behaviour.....	6
2.1.4 Potential toxicology of nTiO ₂ to humans.....	7
2.1.5 Ecological impacts	8
2.2 Nano-cocktail effects	11
2.2.1 Principle	11
2.2.2 Cadmium.....	13
2.2.3 Nano-titanium dioxide and cadmium.....	14
2.3 <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i> as a model organism	15
2.4 Preceding Studies with <i>C. elegans</i>	16
3 Objectives.....	18
4 Materials and Methods.....	20
4.1 Stock preparation of <i>Escherichia coli</i>	20
4.2 Cultivation of <i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>	20
4.3 Test materials.....	21
4.3.1 Titanium dioxide nanoparticles	21
4.3.2 Cadmium.....	22

4.3.3	NS8593.....	22
4.3.4	Lanthanum.....	22
4.3.5	Heparin	22
4.4	Preparation of culture media.....	23
4.5	Simulated solar radiation.....	24
4.6	Chemical characterisation	25
4.6.1	Separation of agglomerates	26
4.6.2	X-ray diffraction	26
4.6.3	Scanning electron microscopy.....	28
4.6.4	Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy	29
4.6.5	Dynamic light scattering.....	29
4.6.6	Zeta potential	31
4.6.7	Photocatalytic activity	32
4.7	Molecular mode of action	33
4.7.1	Rhodamine test	34
4.7.2	Membrane integrity	36
4.7.3	Cell titer assay.....	37
4.8	Statistical analysis	38
5	Chemical characterisation.....	39
5.1	Background	39
5.2	Results.....	41
5.2.1	Crystal structure	41
5.2.2	Agglomeration size	42
5.2.3	Element composition.....	48
5.2.4	Zeta potential	50
5.2.5	Photocatalytic activity	52

5.3	Discussion	55
5.3.1	Crystal structure	55
5.3.2	Agglomeration size	56
5.3.3	Element composition.....	57
5.3.4	Zeta potential	58
5.3.5	Photocatalytic activity	59
6	Molecular mode of action	61
6.1	Background	61
6.2	Results.....	63
6.2.1	The role of free intracellular calcium	63
6.2.2	Membrane integrity	66
6.2.3	Cell viability.....	71
6.3	Discussion	72
6.3.1	The role of free intracellular calcium	72
6.3.2	Membrane integrity	73
6.3.3	Cell viability assay.....	74
7	Conclusion and Outlook	76
8	Bibliography	79
9	Annex.....	88

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Prof. Susanne Heise for her kind acceptance into her working group. With her thematic suggestions, experimental ideas as well as her broad ecotoxicological knowledge, she supported me throughout and encouraged me not to give up.

Thanks to Prof. Andrew Hursthouse for the good supervision, constructive conversations, and support in the PhD programme at UWS.

I would also like to thank my colleagues Sonja Faetsch, Henning Tien and Anne Below. A good conversation always made the day in the lab easier, and a laugh in the office was often very energising.

Thanks to the great support of Dr. Charlotte Ruhmlieb, which made it possible for me to carry out and evaluate all chemical analyses efficiently. She always had an open ear for physical questions. I thank the members of the institute of physical chemistry at the university of Hamburg for giving me access to their technical equipment.

Last but not least, I thank my family and friends for their support in crisis situations, but also in good times.

Maria, you are my emotional support. I am very grateful for you and your love, without which many things would not have been possible. To the moon and back...

To Lilli

Statutory Declaration

I declare that I have authored this thesis independently, that I have not used other than the declared sources and resources, and that I have explicitly marked all material, which has been quoted either literally or by content from the used sources.

Hamburg, 24.09.2023

Personal details withheld.

Lisa Taplick

Summary

The ecological fate of manufactured nanoparticles and contaminants is important for their risk assessment in aquatic environments. Studies of Angelstorf et al. (2014) indicated that nano-titanium dioxide (nTiO₂) is far more toxic to the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) than the bulk material. The co-exposure of nTiO₂ and cadmium ions (Cd²⁺) showed adverse synergistic effects on *C. elegans* under simulated solar radiation (SSR), leading to a inhibition reproduction of 80 % compared to individual exposure (Samet, 2017b). Investigations of nano-cocktail effects are therefore necessary to understand the mode of action and its environmental relevance. This work focuses on the characterisation of irradiated and non-irradiated nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-agglomerates to evaluate SSR-stimulated changes of their chemical characteristics. Different methodological approaches were tested. To examine whether and how SSR has an impact on the chemical structure of the agglomerates, measurements regarding the crystal structure (XRD) size (SEM and DLS), surface charge (zeta potential), photocatalytic activity and element composition (EDX) were performed. In addition, the molecular mode of action was investigated testing ion channel behaviour and membrane integrity of *C. elegans*. The studies of nTiO₂- Cd²⁺-agglomerates at pH values 4 and 7 simulate the influence of the gut passage in *C. elegans* and showed a pH-dependency of the agglomeration size and a Cd²⁺-concentration dependency regarding the photocatalytic activity, but no difference in crystal structure nor SSR-induced changes. Non-reproducible results of experiments regarding the role of calcium ion channels in the toxicity of nTiO₂- Cd²⁺-mixtures, tested with different channel blockers (NS8593 for TRPM7, lanthanum for TRPM3 and heparin for IP₃-receptors) led to the conclusion that the effect on *C. elegans* is rather unspecific. Therefore, the effect of the nano-cocktail under SSR on membrane integrity was tested. A photocatalytic-induced damage of the pharynx and start of the intestine in *C. elegans* became obvious. The combination of nTiO₂, Cd²⁺ and SSR seems to interact with the cells of the early gut system in a pH-dependent and UV-induced photocatalytic matter. Cadmium enhances the photocatalytic activity of nTiO₂ by forming cationic ions, leading to more reactive agglomerates and the observed synergistic effect. The rupture of the cell membrane could explain the increase in toxicity, which then results in the measured inhibition of

reproduction by harming cell proliferation. This offers a better understanding of the active mode of action and a way to evaluate the risk of nanoparticles and contaminants in aqueous milieus.

Index of Symbols and Abbreviations

Symbols

Å	Angstrom
c	speed of light
C	Curie
d	difference between rows of atoms
D	translational diffusion coefficient
d(H)	hydrodynamic diameter
e	charge
f(ka)	henry-relation
h	Planck constant
J _s	Joule second
k	Boltzmann constant
m ₀	electron mass
n	integer
T	temperature
U	electronic potential
ε	dielectric constant
ζ	zeta potential
η	viscosity
θ	X-ray beam angle
λ	wavelength

Abbreviations

bTiO ₂	bulk-sized titanium dioxide
<i>C. elegans</i>	<i>Caenorhabditis elegans</i>
Ca ²⁺	calcium (II)-ions
Cd ²⁺	cadmium (II)-ions
CGC	Caenorhabditis Genetics Center
CHO cells	Chinese Hamster Ovary cells

ddH ₂ O	double-distilled water
DLS	Dynamic Light Scattering
DMSO	Dimethylsulfoxide
<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
EC ₅₀	Median effective concentration
EDX	energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
Hep	heparin
HOMO	highest occupied molecular orbital
L1-L4	Larvae stages
La ³⁺	lanthanum (III)-ions
LB	Lysogeny Broth
LC ₅₀	Median lethal concentration
LD ₅₀	Median lethal dose
LUMO	lowest unoccupied molecular orbital
NGM	Nematode Growth Medium
nTiO ₂	nanoscale titanium dioxide
O/N	overnight
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
PBS	Phosphate Buffered Saline
rpm	revolutions per minute
RT	room temperature
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SSR	Simulated Solar Radiation
TRPM	Transient Receptor Potential Channel Type Melastatin
XRD	X-ray Diffraction
YA	Young Adult

1 Introduction

Every day, our environment is exposed to pollutants, which enter the biological pathways *via* a wide variety of pathways. In addition to the visible pollution of the environment through used oil, chemicals or heavy metals, tiny particles enter our wastewater every day, which can also cause great damage. While it is already difficult to efficiently remove particles the size of a micrometre, it is often impossible handling nanoparticles, as they are even smaller by a factor of 1000 and the existing filter systems are overchallenged with such a small size.

Nanomaterials consist of primary particles with an average size of less than 100 nanometres (Vert et al., 2012). The small size and the associated large surface compared to its weight lead to characteristic features which are different from those of the respective bulk material. They have, for example, different chemical reactivity, fluorescence, and electric conductivity (Becker et al., 2014). The targeted production of nanomaterials aims to use these features for technological approaches, and nanotechnology has become a key technology of the 21st century. Nanomaterials are nowadays used in nanobiotechnology (Maness et al., 1999), nanomedicine (Ren et al., 2015), energy devices (Carbajo et al., 2018), soil remediation (Yang et al., 2017), food (Xie and Hung, 2018), healthcare and cosmetic products (Weir et al., 2012), wastewater treatment (Ahmed and Haider, 2018), as well as in paint (Karlsson et al., 2018), paper (Adel et al., 2016), and plastics productions (Carneiro et al., 2007).

Due to its many applications, nanomaterials inevitably enter the environment (Robichaud et al., 2009). Even though many investigations address the toxicological impact (Petersen and Henry, 2012, Klaine et al., 2012, Bameri et al., 2022), evaluation of their environmental risk suffers from insufficient data on their ecotoxicity (Handy et al., 2012, Guzmán et al., 2006, Nowack et al., 2012) and ecological behaviour (Kahru and Dubourguier, 2010, Sengul and Asmatulu, 2020).

Nanoscale titanium dioxide (nTiO₂) is among the most relevant nanomaterials because of its high production rate (10 000 t in 2012, extrapolation of Sun et al. (2014)), high application rate and special properties (Schaumann et al., 2015). The industry uses the

Introduction

optical transparency of nTiO₂ as UV blockers in sunscreen and cosmetic products, as photocatalyst in solar cells, paints or surface coatings (Klaine et al., 2008).

In applications such as suntan lotion, the nanoparticles are surrounded by a protective layer of aluminium hydroxide Al(OH)₃ so that the human skin is not exposed to the damage caused by photoactivation of nTiO₂ by UV radiation. However, the bonds between these layers and nTiO₂ are only conditionally resistant to water. So that if they remain in water for a longer period of time, this protective layer is detached from nTiO₂ by the surrounding water, and the particles are free and can interact with the pollutants contained in the water (Virkutyte et al., 2012). The consequences of these interactions are still little studied but can affect our environment, so more investigations are needed.

Pollutants like cadmium, a highly toxic representative of the heavy metals, is preferentially deposited in sediments (Müller, 1977). There it can interact with nTiO₂, that has also accumulated there. If tidal flats are formed, as for example in the Elbe River or the North Sea, these complexes are exposed to UV radiation. But this is precisely where there is a gap that makes further research indispensable. How do nanoparticles react with contaminants in the environment, especially in the aqueous milieu, under UV radiation? Are there changes in the chemical behaviour with direct sunlight? How do small invertebrates react to the particles, which are small enough to be ingested by them? Are there risk assessments and studies that evaluate the impact?

This work focuses precisely on these questions. The aim is to clarify whether and how nTiO₂ and the toxic pollutant cadmium change chemically in the aqueous milieu of the environment and agglomerate, and how this affects living organisms such as nematodes, all under the influence of solar radiation.

2 State of the Art

2.1 Titanium dioxide nanoparticles

2.1.1 Crystal structure

Nanoscale titanium dioxide exists in three different crystal structures: anatase, rutile and brookite, it's the latter only being of technical insignificance. The unit cells of rutile and anatase both are built tetragonal with 90° angles, but they differ in the length of their edges and their coordination number.

The length of the edges a and b of the anatase structure are 3.73 \AA , the edge c is 9.37 \AA , thus 2.5 times longer than a and b . In the rutile structure, a and b have an edge length of 4.59 \AA , but the edge c in this structure is 1.6 times smaller than the edges a and b with 2.96 \AA . These length differences result in different crystal structures for rutile nTiO_2 and anatase nTiO_2 . In the anatase crystal, one titanium molecule is surrounded by 4 oxygen atoms, while in the rutile crystal there is a coordination ratio of one titanium to 2 oxygen molecules (Figure 2.1, Table 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Unit cells of the crystal structures of anatase and rutile TiO_2 , based on the coordinate descriptions of Parker (1924) and Baur (1955) using the software Mercury.

State of the Art

Table 2.1: Structure data of anatase and rutile TiO₂, adapted from the coordinate descriptions of Parker (1924) and Baur (1955).

	Anatase	Rutile
Space Group	I 4 ₁ /a m d (tetragonal)	P 4 ₂ /m n m (tetragonal)
Cell Length [Å]	<i>a</i> 3.73, <i>b</i> 3.73, <i>c</i> 9.37	<i>a</i> 4.59, <i>b</i> 4.59, <i>c</i> 2.96
Cell Angles [°]	α 90, β 90, γ 90	α 90, β 90, γ 90
Coordination Number	Z = 4	Z = 2

In a crystalline solid, repulsive, and attractive interactions arrange the atoms periodically. Since the bonds between the single atoms are very small, their outer orbitals overlap and interact with each other. With an increasing number of atoms in a crystal, their individual energy levels are no longer distinguishable, but form broad energy ranges which merge into a continuous band. This band is characterised by two edges: the highest occupied molecule orbital (HOMO) is called the valence band edge, while the lowest unoccupied molecule orbital (LUMO) corresponds to the conduction band edge (Hunklinger, 2017). A nanosized crystal can occur as a metal, a semiconductor, or an insulator as depicted in Figure 2.2. The difference is determined by the energy difference between the HOMO and the LUMO, the band gap E_g . The energy which separates the occupied and unoccupied states at absolute zero point is called the Fermi energy E_F (Figure 2.2). In a metal, the bands overlap, the electrons are at the Fermi level and can move freely through the solid. If the band gap is too large and cannot be overcome, the solid is called an insulator. In a semiconductor, the band gap can be overcome by applying high energy, for example in the form of light. This generates an electron-hole-pair which can move through the structure (Hunklinger, 2017, Bhagyaraj et al., 2018)

State of the Art

Figure 2.2: Schematic portrayal of the band structure of a metal, a semiconductor and an insulator. The dotted line displays the fermi energy E_F , while the black distances describe the band gap E_g .

Nanoscale titanium dioxide is a semiconductor, so the band gap can be overcome, and light is absorbed, which leads to photocatalytic properties.

2.1.2 Photocatalytic activity

The production of TiO_2 nanomaterials was enhanced mostly because of their photocatalytic capacities: bulk (b) TiO_2 has a limited photocatalytic activity because the band gap is relatively big: 3.0 eV for rutile, 3.2 eV for anatase (Nam et al., 2019). Band gaps determine the absorption capacities of a substance and determine the amount of energy that is needed to overcome the barrier and for the substance to become photocatalytically active. b TiO_2 cannot absorb visible light efficiently, only the smaller wavelengths of 380 to 500 nm (blue light), making it suitable for light protection in paints (Nam et al., 2019). By having a higher surface-to-volume ratio, n TiO_2 has proven to slightly enhance the photocatalytic effect by a higher amount of reactive sites (Miyoshi et al., 2020). One method to enhance the performance of nanoparticles is to couple the two most active crystallisation phases, rutile (14%) and anatase (86%), creating the P25 compound (Aeroxide® Degussa) which is also used in this work (Nam et al., 2019).

Evonik Operations GmbH (2021) describes Aeroxide® TiO_2 P25 as a fine-particle pure titanium dioxide with a high specific surface area and pronounced aggregate and agglomerate structure. Due to its high purity, large specific surface area and

combination of anatase and rutile crystal structure, it can be used for many catalytic and photocatalytic applications as well as for UV filters.

One main goal in current research is to generate new methods to destroy pollutants, and nTiO₂ has proven itself as an effective substance to clean organic pollutants (Li et al., 2020). When nTiO₂ is activated by light with an energy greater than its band gap, electrons are transferred from the valence band to the conduction band. At the same time, electron holes maintain in the valence band. The electrons and holes then generate radicals that lead to the decomposition of organic pollutants by oxidation and reduction, resulting in harmless products, such as carbon dioxide and water (Figure 2.3) (Serpone and Emeline, 2002). But there's a need to examine the impact of nTiO₂ when used for remediation on aquatic microbiota, mainly the eukaryotic *C. elegans*, and on organic material which benefits the environment.

Figure 2.3: Principle of photoactivation of nTiO₂ to neutralize organic pollutants, adapted from descriptions of Serpone and Emeline (2002).

2.1.3 Primary particles and agglomeration behaviour

As mentioned in the introduction, the definition of a nanoparticle is based on its primary particle size of a single particle, which needs to be less than 100 nm (Vert et al., 2012). But nTiO₂ does not occur as single particles, but forms agglomerates and aggregates, the so-called secondary particles. They are formed by primary particles which are held by weak van-der-Waals forces (agglomerates) or strong chemical bonds (aggregates) (Jiang et al., 2008). The size of the secondary particles is defined by these forces and is often in micrometre range (Shi et al., 2013). When the particles are dispersed in liquids, the size is determined by the hydrodynamic diameter, and with a low surface charge, a thinner double layer and no steric forces, the preferred configuration for nTiO₂ is agglomeration (Jiang et al., 2008).

2.1.4 Potential toxicology of nTiO₂ to humans

Various studies were undertaken regarding the potential toxicology of nTiO₂ to humans. The main routes encounter inhalation and dermal exposure of aerosols, suspensions and emulsions of reagents containing nTiO₂ (Shakeel et al., 2016).

As nTiO₂ is commonly used as inorganic UV absorbers in sunscreen products, the dermal exposure is of high interest (Jaroenworuluck et al., 2006, Lewicka et al., 2011). The application on skin is normally safe, but if the skin is injured, for example by sunburn or violation, the safety cannot be ensured (Monteiro-Riviere et al., 2011). Sadrieh et al. (2010) discovered elevated titanium levels in treated epidermis tissue of minipigs, while Bennat and Müller-Goymann (2000) measured a penetration through hairy human skin if an oil-in-water emulsion of nTiO₂ is used. But not only damaged skin is susceptible to the toxic influence of nTiO₂: after exposing mouse skin to nTiO₂ over a longer period of time, induced levels of oxidative stress were measured inside the organism and this may also pose a health risk to humans (Wu et al., 2009).

Another exposure route is ingestion *via* inhalation. While there is no data regarding the absorption of nTiO₂ in humans, studies with especially rodents are manyfold (Kuempel et al., 2006). The main distribution was detected in lungs and the mediastinal lymph node (Mühlfeld et al., 2007, van Ravenzwaay et al., 2009). The dose-dependent deposition of titanium was measured in lung tissue of mice, leading to inflammatory effects (Ma-Hock et al., 2009, Lindberg et al., 2012). The up-regulation of lung neurotrophins, measured in different age stages of rats, could lead to a higher risk of developing asthma bronchiale (Scuri et al., 2010).

In addition to these major routes, nasal and oral ingestions, injections and prenatal exposures are possible, but do not pose a direct risk to humans (Shakeel et al., 2016).

2.1.5 Ecological impacts

Nanoscale titanium dioxide is of ecological importance because of its high predicted accumulation rates in European river sediments of up to $2 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}\text{yr}^{-1}$ (Sun et al., 2014) compared to other nanomaterials. This is due to its increasing production rate over the last decades, which was estimated to be about 2.5 million tons by 2025 (Robichaud et al., 2009). The accumulation mostly takes place in soils, where for example sewage sludge is amended, and was predicted to reach a few thousand milligram per kilogram soil (Gottschalk et al., 2015, Priester et al., 2013).

For a full evaluation of the environmental and ecological impact of a substance, it is important to outline the steps which are already taken to ensure its safety. Therefore, a search for existing publications focusing on the risk assessment of nTiO₂ in the environment was conducted. Using the search tool *Scopus* and the keywords `nTiO₂ OR nano-titanium dioxide OR nano-TiO₂ AND environment`, 562 documents were found from 2004 till July 2023. Narrowing down the search by adding the keyword `toxicity`, the results were reduced to 181. Going further, with the keyword `risk assessment`, only 29 publications were submitted. Lastly, the keyword `impact` was added, which results in just 14 documents (Figure 2.4). At the end, the search in combination with `sublethal effects` led to no results, which indicates a gap in research. However, it is precisely the sublethal effects and their mode of action that are important in order to represent a hazard for organisms and to be able to carry out an accurate risk assessment.

State of the Art

Figure 2.4: Scopus search for publications with the keywords 'nano-titanium dioxide OR nTiO₂ OR nano-TiO₂' AND environment, then adding stepwise the keywords 'toxicity', 'risk assessment' and 'impact', performed on July 6th, 2023.

Average EC₅₀-values in the higher ppm-range from 10 to 100 mg/L classify nTiO₂ as a "harmful substance" (Kahru and Dubourguier, 2010). The exact mechanism of the toxic effect, however, is widely unknown (Smijis and Pavel, 2011), but its photocatalytic property may play a role due to the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Maness et al., 1999). They could lead to an increased level of oxidative stress and oxidative damage in cell structures, which was observed after exposure to nTiO₂ (Schmid et al., 2009). But it is still not proven if this is the decisive process and further evaluations on the possible mode of action need to be performed.

Another ecological aspect that is little known but of potentially high importance is the interaction of nTiO₂ with other environmental contaminants: Due to its large and reactive surface relative to its mass, nTiO₂ could interact with inorganic and organic

State of the Art

potential pollutants *via* van-der-Waals-interactions and electrostatic attraction and transport them using a 'Trojan-horse effect' – maybe even in animal and plant cells (Naasz et al., 2018). The amount of studies facing mixture toxicities is still small, and more investigations of 'nano-cocktail' effects have been called for (Hartmann and Baun, 2010).

2.2 Nano-cocktail effects

2.2.1 Principle

In our anthropogenic environment, many human-caused pollutants are found in different compartments, e.g., a large number of pesticides in soils (Gunstone et al., 2021), combinations of potentially effective, accumulated heavy metals in sediments (Huang et al., 2020) or increased concentrations of nutrients in water causing a lack of oxygen (Chislock et al., 2013). To estimate the risk for different species, many different combinations of contaminants would have to be tested. And the steps that need to be required from lab to the environmental risk assessment start with cell and bacterial testing, followed by experiments on nematodes and invertebrates over small mammals to humans.

But this high amount of studies is not possible, therefore, ecotoxicological models and classification systems for mixing toxicology assessments were developed (Spurgeon et al., 2010). The most common patterns are the concentration-addition (CA) model for pollutants with similar modes of actions and the independent-action (IA) model, which describes different mechanisms of action. If substances interact, it further leads to additive, antagonistic or synergistic effects. Hartmann and Baun (2010) display seven different scenarios of effects of nanoparticles in combination with pollutants (Figure 2.5):

- 1) There is no interaction between the nanoparticles (NP) and the environmental contaminant (EC). The EC has an effect on the organism which is not disturbed by the NP. The NP itself has no effect on the organism.
- 2) Both EC and NP have separate effects on the organisms with a possible uptake, but no direct interaction between them.
- 3) A direct interaction between NP, EC and organisms occurs: the NP increase the bioavailability of the EC by increasing their local concentration.
- 4) In this case, the uptake, effect, and bioavailability of the EC is increased as a result of a membrane rupture of the organism, caused directly or indirectly by the NP.
- 5) The NP and EC interact, and the EC enters the organism *via* a “Trojan-horse effect”, which facilitates the uptake.

- 6) Free ions (Me^{n+}) are released from the NP, which compete for binding sites with the EC. The uptake and effect of EC is decreased. The overall effect of the organism can be either decreased, unchanged or increased depending on the specific properties of the substances.
- 7) The EC are sorbed onto the NP outside the organisms, leading to a reduced bioavailability of the EC, the effect of the NP on the organism is possibly inherent.

Figure 2.5: Different scenarios of nanoparticles (NP) acting as modifying factors on the effect of environmental contaminants (EC) toward an organism. 1: no interaction between NP and EC. The EC has an effect on the organism which is not disturbed by the NP. The NP itself has no effect on the organism. 2: both EC and NP have separate effects on the organisms with a possible uptake, but no direct interaction. 3: direct interaction between NP, EC and organisms occurs: the NP increase the bioavailability of the EC by increasing their local concentration. 4: the uptake, effect, and bioavailability of the EC is increased as a result of a membrane rupture of the organism, caused directly or indirectly by the NP. 5: NP and EC interact, a Trojan-horse mechanism facilitates the uptake of NP-EC-complexes. 6: free ions (Me^{n+}) are released from the NP, which compete for binding sites with the EC, decreasing the uptake and effect of EC. The overall effect of the organism can be either decreased, unchanged or increased depending on the specific properties of the substances. 7: EC are sorbed onto the NP outside the organisms, leading to a reduced bioavailability of the EC, the effect of the NP on the organism is possibly inherent. Adapted from Hartmann and Baun (2010).

While adsorption of metal ions on TiO_2 nanoparticles has been well documented (Engates and Shipley, 2011), the effect of the photocatalytic activity of $nTiO_2$ is still not adequately investigated. There are just a few studies which correlate the influence of solar radiation on the combinatorial impact, although this property may lead to heavy-

metal enrichment in organisms or it may detoxify and thus reduce the impact (Jovanović, 2015). This thesis specifically focusses on the nano-cocktail effect of nTiO₂ with cadmium, a heavy metal which, despite its known high toxicity and strict waste regulations, is still frequently found in sediments of rivers and seas due to industrial pollution (Schütze et al., 2003). Therefore, its ecological relevance is still very high.

2.2.2 Cadmium

Cadmium (Cd) is a heavy metal which was used mainly for batteries, accumulators, rust protection and colour pigments (Martelli et al., 2006), but because of its classification as a human carcinogen, it has lost its importance in technology applications (Waalke, 2003). But there are still a lot of cadmium-containing electronic devices like batteries or televisions, which enter the environment and can cause damage to plants and animals. It is known that cadmium disrupts physiological signal transduction mechanisms in living organisms, which leads to a permanent disruption of transducing modules in signalling, for example second messengers get elevated or decreased (Thévenod, 2009). A release of intracellular calcium ions from internal stores was observed (Kiss and Osipenko, 1994). In aqueous milieu, cadmium occurs mainly as the divalent cation form Cd²⁺ (Kubier et al., 2019). These are similar in size and charge to the cell-necessary cations zinc (Zn²⁺) and calcium (Ca²⁺) and can thus be taken up by the cell *via a Trojan horse* mechanism. The defence mechanisms of the cells are thus bypassed and cadmium enters the cytoplasm (Martelli et al., 2006). For the environment and its living beings, cadmium is a potential problem: due to its slow degradation rate in ecological systems, cadmium cumulates in soil and sediment and is available for uptake for long periods of time (Goering et al., 1994).

Guidelines for drinking-water quality, provided by the World Health Organisation (WHO) in 2011, recommend a maximal value of 0.003 mg/L for cadmium, in Germany they range from 0.00011 to 0.0027 mg/L (Duijnsveld et al., 2008) depending on the geological conditions. In sediments and soils, cadmium occurs in a wide range of 0.01 up to 1 mg/kg dry weight, which is partly due to the comparatively high concentration of natural occurring cadmium salts in the earth's crust of 0.2 mg/kg dry weight (Kubier et al., 2019).

In the *Gestis* substance database (<https://gestis.dguv.de>), toxicological data for cadmium regarding various living organisms and various studies are listed: the LD₅₀ for rats (oral) is measured at 2330 mg/kg dry weight (Technical Database Services (TDS), New York, 2009), which is relatively high compared to the toxicological data for marine specimen: for the fish species glass perch (*Priopidichthys marianus*) and diamond-scaled mullet (*Liza vaigiensis*), LC₅₀ values were published in the range of 0.001 to 45 mg/L (Denton and Burdon-Jones, 1986). Studies on different crustaceans showed an huge LC₅₀ span of 0.000072 up to 4 mg/L (*Mysidopsis bahia*) (Ward, 1989) and an EC₅₀ of 0.58 mg/L (*Daphnia obtusa*) (Rossini and Ronco, 1996). *Rhaphidocelis subcapitata*, a microalga, provides EC₅₀ values between 0.097 and 0.452 mg/L (Van der Heever and Grobbelaar, 1996). The nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans* shows a higher tolerance to cadmium compared to other heavy metals (Roh et al., 2006) with an EC₅₀ of 0.7 mg/L (Höss et al., 2011).

2.2.3 Nano-titanium dioxide and cadmium

Due to contamination of aquatic systems with nTiO₂ and increased concentrations of heavy metals in industrial or mining-influenced waters, many different authors examined combination effects on mainly aquatic organisms. Present results, however, are controversial. A review by Deng et al. (2017) described both increasing and inhibiting effects of nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-combinations compared to single exposures on different species: nTiO₂ can enhance the toxic impact of cadmium, observed by Yang et al. (2014) regarding the growth inhibition of the ciliate *Tetrahymena thermophila* with eight different Cd²⁺ concentrations from 0 up to 2 mg/L and three nTiO₂ concentrations (0, 1.3 and 13.2 mg/L).

But the opposite effect has also been reported: in different studies, 100 mg/L of nTiO₂ reduced the growth inhibition effect of 1-3 mg/L Cd²⁺ in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (Yang et al., 2012a) and in *Oryza sativa* at Cd²⁺ concentrations of 10 and 20 mg/L and nTiO₂ concentrations from 0 to 1000 mg/L (Ji et al., 2017).

Balbi et al. (2014) reported on experiments with bivalve species *Mytilus galloprovincialis* that 0.1 mg/L cadmium inhibited the nTiO₂-induced rise of immune parameters (NO-

production, lysosome activity) and the nano-cocktail affected embryonal development at nTiO₂ concentrations of 0.1 mg/L.

nTiO₂ can also have an influence on the bioaccumulation of cadmium: Zhang et al. (2007) described increased absorption of Cd²⁺ (0.1 mg/L) by carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) in presence of nTiO₂ (10 mg/L) by 146%. Hartmann et al. (2012) showed similar results with water fleas (*Daphnia magna*), but not for gloss worms (*Lumbricus variegatus*) at concentrations of 2 mg/L nTiO₂ and 0.1 to 1.6 mg/L Cd²⁺. The uptake of nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-complexes is more effective for *D. magna* because of its feeding behaviour, large particles would exceed the mouth size of *L. variegatus*. nTiO₂ also promoted the bioaccumulation of Cd²⁺ by 46.8% in *T. thermophila* (Yang et al., 2014). Effects on membrane structures were also described: by forming complexes with cell membranes, nTiO₂ (100 mg/L) promoted the accumulation of Cd²⁺ (100 mg/L) in *C. reinhardtii* and led to increased membrane permeability (Yang et al., 2012b).

There are some scenarios, that needed special conditions for the complexes to have an effect: the enhancement of Cd²⁺ accumulation and toxicity by a sediment concentration of 3.22 mg/L nTiO₂ in *Bellamyia aeruginosa* was only significant at pH 9 (Ma et al., 2017), while a different particle size from 1 to 10 nm of nTiO₂ (4 mg/L) had different influences on the bioaccumulation of 0.2 and 2 mg/L Cd²⁺ in *D. magna* (Tan et al., 2017).

2.3 *Caenorhabditis elegans* as a model organism

The roundworm *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) was chosen as a model organism for ecotoxicological experiments. It is a free-living representative of nematodes, the most diverse and abundant group of metazoans in sediments and soils of the temperate zone (Traunspurger et al., 1995). Because of early sequencing of the whole genome in 1998, *C. elegans* is very attractive as a research object (Hope, 1999). Additionally, its laboratory cultivation is unproblematic and many important physiological processes, e.g. cellular signalling pathways, are similar to humans, therefore *C. elegans* became an important test organism in pharmacological studies (Baumeister, 2005). For ecotoxicological testing, it is used to evaluate the effect of polluted sediments and soils (Traunspurger et al., 1997). The ISO 10872 (2010-06) describes an established method to gather information about chronic toxicity of solid substrates and solutions.

C. elegans is a useful model for toxicity studies: The roundworm is transparent, so inner organs as pharynx and intestine are visible microscopically (Figure 2.6). Based on fast defecation cycles, uptake and excretion of test substances can be monitored exactly.

Figure 2.6: Schematic depiction of an adult hermaphrodite with (1) ovary, (2) intestine, (3) pharynx, (4) oviduct, (5) oocytes, (6) uterus, (7) eggs, (8) vulva, (9) rectum and (10) anus (ISO-10872, 2010).

2.4 Preceding Studies with *C. elegans*

This thesis is based on two previous dissertations. Investigations of Angelstorf (2013) focussed on the chronic toxicity of bulk and nano-sized titanium dioxide on *C. elegans* under dark and irradiated conditions. The results under dark conditions provided that nTiO₂, with an EC₅₀ of > 100 mg/L, is far more toxic to the nematode than bTiO₂, which showed no toxic effect. The effect of nTiO₂ is enhanced when the test organisms are exposed to 30 minutes of simulated solar radiation (SSR) during their 72-hour lifespan, resulting in an EC₅₀ of 53 mg/L. The toxicity of bTiO₂ is not influenced by light conditions either. These results correlate with the photocatalytic properties of nTiO₂ which are missing in bTiO₂ and could cause oxidative stress. But investigations focussing on cellular stress markers showed no indication for that and no production of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Assumptions on the mode of action therefore include an extracellular oxidative damage of intestinal epithelial cells because microscopic observations showed an accumulation of nanoparticles in the intestine of *C. elegans*.

Further studies by Samet (2017a) examined a potential influence of SSR on mixtures of nTiO₂ and cadmium (Cd), a heavy metal known for its toxic impact e.g. in sediments of the Elbe river (Heise et al., 2007). Cd²⁺ is known to induce intracellular calcium (Ca²⁺) signal pathways because of protective cell processes (Thévenod, 2009). Therefore, Samet (2017a) investigated the effect of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ on the amount of intracellular

State of the Art

calcium *via* rhodamine, a fluorescent dye. The results showed a decrease of intracellular calcium concentration when co-exposed, whereas single exposure led to an increase. Regulated intracellular calcium levels control a large number of cellular processes, for example fertilisation, gene expression, proliferation and cell motility. Ca^{2+} ions work as secondary messengers and their concentration is changed referring to a primary signal (Berridge et al., 2000). So the presence of nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} can be sensed by the cell, which reacts by decreasing intracellular calcium levels. Samet (2017a) also observed a decrease in reproduction of *C. elegans* of 80% under simulated solar radiation compared to dark conditions. These two results may be based on a receptor which controls Ca^{2+} homeostasis as well as reproduction. After further literature review, a gene (*gon-2*) was found which codes a cation channel (GON-2) of TRPM (transient receptor potential type melastatin) proteins. It is located in the intestine of *C. elegans*. GON-2 imparts the influx of Ca^{2+} ions into gonadal precursor cells of *C. elegans*, hence it makes significant contributions to the development of fertility in nematodes (Church and Lambie, 2003). It is known that nTiO_2 can have a toxic impact on cells and membranes due to its photocatalytic activity (Church and Lambie, 2003), but the influence of Cd^{2+} is still unknown.

3 Objectives

Synergistic impacts which cannot be explained *via* a concentration addition or independent action model indicate an interaction between single stress components. Spurgeon et al. (2010) described three different potentially underlying processes (Figure 3.1):

- 1) Interaction of pollutants in soils and pore water outside the organism which leads to an increase or decrease of environmental availability, for example bonds, speciation, or transport to the organism.
- 2) Toxicokinetic processes inside the organism which lead to a different uptake into cells, different transport inside the organism or excretion changes.
- 3) Toxicodynamic processes of physiologic target regions, for example activation or deactivation of a receptor which leads to a wrong signal pathway and indicates a toxic impact.

Figure 3.1: Schematic view of mixing toxicities, focusing environmental availability (1), toxicokinetic (2) and toxicodynamic (3) processes. Adapted from (Spurgeon et al., 2010).

This work addresses all three described processes with different hypotheses and experimental approaches (Table 3.1):

Objectives

Table 3.1: Objectives, the resulting hypotheses, and the chosen experimental methods of this work

Objective	Hypothesis	Method
<p>1 Influence of form and structure of nTiO₂-Cd²⁺ agglomerates on environmental availability</p>	<p>"Irradiation changes crystal structure, agglomeration size and relative element composition of agglomerates, leading to increased toxicity."</p>	<p>Measurements of agglomeration size, crystal structure, binding situations, surface charge and photocatalytic capacities at pH 4 and 7 under dark and irradiated conditions</p>
<p>2 Toxicokinetic processes inside the organism are disturbed regarding</p> <p>a) calcium-dependent receptors on the surface of cells</p> <p>b) the cell membrane integrity</p>	<p>"Gon-2 calcium ion channels play a relevant role in the synergistic inhibitory effect of nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-mixtures on <i>C. elegans</i> under simulated solar radiation."</p> <p>"The mixture of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ under simulated solar radiation ruptures the membrane of intestinal cells of <i>C. elegans</i>, leading to an uptake of toxic Cd²⁺ into the cell."</p>	<p>Experiments on free intracellular calcium levels with combinations of nTiO₂, Cd²⁺ and antagonists of different calcium ion channels with adult <i>C. elegans</i></p> <p>Measurements of membrane integrity of adult <i>C. elegans</i> with propidium iodide with and without irradiation</p>
<p>3 By entering specific cells, toxicodynamic processes are activated</p>	<p>"The effect of the mixture under simulated solar radiation on cells like CHO is comparable to those on <i>C. elegans</i>, which would describe a toxicodynamic effect."</p>	<p>Cell viability assay with CHO K1 cells under dark and irradiated conditions</p>

4 Materials and Methods

4.1 Stock preparation of *Escherichia coli*

Escherichia coli is a non-pathogen, gram-negative anaerobic bacterium existing in the gastrointestinal tract of organisms and serves as a food organism for *Caenorhabditis elegans*. To prepare an overnight (O/N) culture, 20 μ L of *E. coli* (OP₅₀, *Caenorhabditis elegans* Center (CGC)) were added to 50 mL sterile Lysogeny Broth-medium (LB, Table 4.4) and incubated for 18 h at 37 °C and 240 rpm shaking. At stationary phase, 1 mL of O/N culture with 20% glycerine was filled into 1.5 mL tubes and stored for up to six months at -20 °C (10872, 2010-06, Angelstorf et al., 2014).

4.2 Cultivation of *Caenorhabditis elegans*

This study used the wild-type “Maupas, N2 var. Bristol” (CGC). To cultivate *C. elegans*, an O/N culture of *E. coli* was prepared as described in chapter 4.1. After incubation, 500 μ L of the O/N culture was pipetted on a Nematode Growth Medium (NGM, Table 4.2) agar plate and evenly spread using a Drigalski spatula. The plates were incubated for three hours to achieve a uniform bacterial lawn. *C. elegans* were transferred from an at least 21-day old NGM agar plates using a sterilized scalpel. Small agar blocks (1x2 cm) from the old plates were cut and positioned reversely on the new plate with the bacterial lawn. The nematodes passed through a whole life cycle (Figure 4.1) So after 72 h of incubation at 22 °C, adult nematodes will have developed and were ready to use (10872, 2010-06) in the experiments.

Materials and Methods

Figure 4.1: Life cycle of *C. elegans* (WormAtlas et al., 2017).

4.3 Test materials

4.3.1 Titanium dioxide nanoparticles

The titanium dioxide nanoparticles were provided as part of the OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) programme and were characterised by Evonik Degussa in January 2019 to exclude aging or decomposition of the material. Their crystal structure is a composition of 86% anatase and 14% rutile, called P25. The analytic data are listed below (Table 4.1)

To prepare a 400 mg/L stock solution, 0.004 g of Titanium dioxide P25 AEROXIDE® (Evonik Degussa) were dissolved in 10 mL ultra-pure water or M9 medium. The solution was mixed for 1 min with a magnetic stirrer, then ultra-sonicated in an ultrasonic bath for five minutes and 320 W at room temperature. The dispersion should rest at least 10 minutes before usage. In the experiments, a standard concentration of 40 mg/L was used.

Materials and Methods

Table 4.1: Physical and chemical parameters of nTiO₂, provided by Evonik Degussa to evaluate the quality of the HAW sample in comparison to the original product from the OECD programme.

Product	units	AEROXIDE TiO ₂ P 25 (OECD programme)	AEROXIDE TiO ₂ P 25 (Sample HAW Hamburg)	spec. limits and target values
Manufacturer		YOK	YOK	
Version		UB 7011	AN 100793-01	
LOT		4168112198	4168112198	
BET specific surface area	m ² /g	57	55	35 – 65
pH-Value		3.6	3.6	3.5 – 4.5
Moisture	%	1.2	1.1	≤ 1.5
Loss on ignition	%	1.1	1.0	≤ 2.0

4.3.2 Cadmium

Cadmium stock suspension was prepared by diluting 274.4 mg Cd(NO₃)₂ · 4 H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich) in 100 mL ultra-pure H₂O with 20 µL HNO₃ (65%), resulting in a Cd²⁺ concentration of 1 g/L. The differently concentrated Cd²⁺-solutions used in the experiments were prepared directly before the tests.

4.3.3 NS8593

The stock solution I (1 g/L) of the TRPM7 channel blocker NS8593 (N-[(1R)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalen-1-yl]-1H-benzimidazol-2-amine, Alomone Labs) was prepared by dissolving 5 mg of the substance in 5 mL DMSO (100 mM). A second stock solution of 50 mg/L was prepared by adding 9.5 mL ultra-pure water to 0.5 mL of stock solution I. Both were stored at -20 °C.

4.3.4 Lanthanum

The lanthanum stock solution with a concentration of 89.35 mg/L was prepared by mixing 8.94 mg LaCl₃ · 7 H₂O (Roth) in 100 mL ultra-pure H₂O.

4.3.5 Heparin

To achieve three different Heparin concentrations, 8 mg, 4 mg and 2 mg Heparin sodium salt (Roth) were diluted in 100 mL ultra-pure H₂O and stored at -20 °C.

4.4 Preparation of culture media

Nematode Growth Medium (NGM) - Agar Plates

Table 4.2: Chemical composition of the NGM-Agar dissolved in 900 mL ultra-pure water.

Chemical substance	g /L
Casein peptone	2.5
Bacteriological agar	17
Sodium chloride (NaCl)	3

Table 4.3: Chemical stock solutions added to the NGM-Agar dissolved in 1000 mL ultra-pure water.

Stock solution	mL
Cholesterol	1
Calcium chloride ($\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$)	1
Magnesium sulphate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$)	1
Potassium phosphate (K_2HPO_4)	25

Lysogeny Broth (LB) Medium

Table 4.4: Chemical composition of the LB-medium in 1000 mL ultra-pure water.

Chemical substance	g /L
Casein Peptone	10
Yeast Extract	5
Sodium chloride (NaCl)	10

M9 medium*Table 4.5: Chemical composition of the M9 medium in ultra-pure water.*

Chemical substance	g/L
Disodium phosphate (Na_2HPO_4)	6
Dipotassium phosphate (K_2HPO_4)	3
Sodium chloride (NaCl)	5
Magnesium sulphate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$)	0.25

Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS)*Table 4.6: Chemical composition of PBS in 1000 mL ultra-pure water.*

Chemical substance	g /L
Disodium hydrogenphosphate (Na_2HPO_4)	10.9
Sodium dihydrogenphosphate ($\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$)	3.68
Sodium chloride (NaCl)	90

4.5 Simulated solar radiation

To simulate the full light spectrum of the sun including ultraviolet, visible and infrared radiation, a Q-Sun Xenon-1-B test chamber with Daylight Q filter (Q-Labs Germany) was used. It includes an 1800 W xenon arc lamp and a chiller to cool down and ensure constant temperatures. To avoid evaporation of medium in the test wells, a quartz plate (EN08: 350 x 220 x 3 ± 0.3 mm, Aachener Quarz-Glas Technologie Heinrich) was used which is permeable for 390 nm, the excitation radiation of nTiO_2 . An external calibration was performed in advance of every experiment, using a radiometer (CR20, Auto Cal) and adjusting the intensity of the radiation at 340 nm to $0.2 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$. All tests were conducted at a temperature set at 12 °C, ensuring 20 °C in the wells due to the heating of the panel by the irradiated light, for a duration of 0, 30 or 60 minutes.

4.6 Chemical characterisation

Figure 4.2: Analytical methods used to characterise the samples.

Table 4.7: Overview of the different analytical methods, the used concentrations of $n\text{TiO}_2$ and Cd^{2+} and the different test conditions.

Method	[$n\text{TiO}_2$]	[Cd^{2+}]	pH value	conditions
XRD	40 mg/L	1 mg/L	pH 4 and 7	dark and SSR
SEM	40 mg/L	1 mg/L	pH 4 and 7	dark and SSR
DLS	40 mg/L	10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 10 mg/L	pH 7	dark and SSR
EDX	40 mg/L	1 mg/L	pH 4 and 7	dark and SSR
Zeta potential	40 mg/L	10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 10 mg/L	pH 4 and 7	dark and SSR
Photocatalytic activity	40 mg/L	10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 1 mg/L	pH 7	SSR

4.6.1 Separation of agglomerates

For characterisation of $n\text{TiO}_2\text{-Cd}^{2+}$ -agglomerates, they needed to be separated from the primary particles and concentrated. This was done by vacuum filtration onto a polycarbonate membrane, applying a Büchner funnel (Figure 1.2). The suspended samples were filtrated and dried before analysis. In order to separate only agglomerates and no single particles, a vacuum pump membrane filtration was performed. The system was built of different components (Lorenz et al., 2006): The vacuum pump was connected to the filtration flask (Büchner flask) which is closed with the base. The base includes a rubber bung and the filter head which was plugged due to a clamp with the funnel (Büchner funnel).

The polycarbonate membrane filter (Whatman™ Circles Cyclopore PC) with a diameter of 25 mm and a pore size of 0.2 μm was fixed with a clamp between the funnel and the filtration head on the porous plate. Prior to filtration, all samples were prepared in M9 medium (Table 4.5), incubated for 3 hours to obtain optimal agglomeration, and either irradiated for 30 minutes or left in the dark. The membrane was dried, and the samples were used for further analysis.

4.6.2 X-ray diffraction

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to gain information on the crystal structure of crystals or powders. The method is based on short wavelengths of X-rays because they correspond to the common atomic plane gaps of the crystals. The characteristic radiation of an X-ray tube passes a filter and an aperture system before it impinges on the sample. If the Bragg equation (1) is fulfilled, the radiation reflects at the atomic planes (Krischner and Koppelhuber-Bitschnau, 1994) as shown in Figure 4.3.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

$$n \cdot \lambda = 2d \cdot \sin \theta \quad (1)$$

In the Bragg equation, d symbolises the difference between planes of atoms, λ the characteristic wavelength of the X-rays impinging on the crystalline sample, n is an integer and θ the angle between the incoming X-ray beam and the crystal. In the simplest instance, an X-ray diffraction experiment consists of a set of diffracted intensities and the angles at which they are observed. This diffraction pattern can be thought of as a chemical fingerprint, and chemical identification can be performed by comparing this diffraction pattern to a database of known patterns.

For this analysis, four different samples were prepared: mixtures of $n\text{TiO}_2$ (40 mg/L) and Cd^{2+} (1 mg/L) at pH 4 and 7, with and without 30 minutes of irradiation. This measurement was executed at the laboratory of Prof. Betzel at the DESY (Deutsches Elektronensynchrotron). The transmission was measured using CuK_α radiation with a wavelength of 1.5404 Å (Incoatec, 50 kV, 1000 µA). The dried samples were fixed at the end of a glass capillary (Glass Number 50 Capillaries, Hampton Research, 0.1 mm external diameter, 0.01 mm wall thickness). During the measurement time of 5 minutes, the capillary performed a volte-face. The signal was detected by an optical disk detector (MAR300, Marresearch marXperts).

All raw data were analysed using the software FIT2D (European Synchrotron Radiation Facility) and calibrating with a Cerium oxide (CeO_2) standard. The program uses a 2-dimensional fitting of data models, in this case the measured data in comparison to the standard values.

4.6.3 Scanning electron microscopy

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is used to gain insight of the topological surface of a sample with high resolution. An electron beam screens the sample and translates electronic interactions into images. The electrons move wave-like, following the De-Broglie equation (2):

$$\lambda = \frac{h}{p} = \frac{h}{m_0 v} = \frac{h}{\sqrt{2m_0 eU}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{eU}{2m_0 c^2}}} \quad (2)$$

λ describes the electronic wavelength, h is the Planck constant ($6.6 \cdot 10^{-34}$ Js), m_0 the mass of an electron ($9.1 \cdot 10^{-31}$ kg), e describes the elementary charge ($1.6 \cdot 10^{-19}$ C), U the electronic potential of the electron source and c is the speed of light ($3.0 \cdot 10^8$ ms⁻¹).

The emitting primary electrons are accelerated *via* adjustable direct current voltage and focused by lenses through electric and magnetic fields (Figure 4.4):

Figure 4.4: Schematic portrayal of SEM (adapted from Seyforth, 2015).

When the electron beam meets the sample, secondary electrons are generated and detected by a detector. The amount of energy of these electrons define the contrast and is translated into high-resolution images (Seyforth, 2015). The dried samples were

dissolved in Methanol, dropped onto 625 μm thick, prime grade silicon wafers (Addison Engineering Inc. San Jose, CA). Again, four different samples were prepared: mixtures of nTiO_2 (40 mg/L) and Cd^{2+} (1 mg/L) at pH 4 and 7, with and without 30 minutes of irradiation. After the samples dried, they were investigated using a Zeiss LEO 1550 with a beam energy of 20 kV at a chamber pressure of approx. $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mbar.

4.6.4 Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy

The principle of energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) is nearly the same as for SEM, but instead of secondary electrons, X-radiation is detected when the electron beam hits the sample. An electron of an inner shell is struck out and an excited state is generated. This gap is filled with an electron with higher energy and an X-ray quant is sent out. This intrinsic radiation is specific for every element, so the exact element composition can be displayed (Macherauch and Zoch, 2011). For the determination of the elemental composition of the four samples, EDX spectroscopy was conducted on a Zeiss EVO-Ma using 22 kV beam energy and a scan time of 180 s per measurement. The preparation followed the same procedure as described for SEM measurement (Chapter 4.6.3)

4.6.5 Dynamic light scattering

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) was used to measure the size of the $\text{nTiO}_2\text{-Cd}^{2+}$ -agglomerates. The Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern) measures random movements of particles (Brownian motion) and relates this to the size of the agglomerates. The sizes of the particles were calculated using the Stokes-Einstein equation (3):

$$d(H) = \frac{kT}{3\pi\eta D} \quad (3)$$

where $d(H)$ describes the hydrodynamic diameter, D the translational diffusion coefficient, k the Boltzmann's constant, T the absolute temperature and η the viscosity (Malvern). The schematic construction (Figure 4.5) includes a laser on the top with helium-neon gas, a wavelength of 633 nm and a maximal output power of 4 mW. The

Materials and Methods

attenuator protects the detector, which records the scattered information in an angle of 173 °. Small particles need more exposure to reflect a high volume of scattered light and it takes more time to saturate the attenuator. The transmission range varies between 100 to 0.0003% (Malvern). The signal, including the intensity of the scattered light, is detected and calculated *via* computer using the Zetasizer Software v.702 (Malvern).

Figure 4.5: Optical configuration of the Zetasizer Nano ZS for DLS measurements (Malvern, 2004).

The samples were prepared by diluting 40 mg/L nTiO₂ and different concentrations of Cd²⁺ (10 µg/L to 10 mg/L) in M9 medium. After two hours of agglomeration, they were put in 1.5 mL semi-micro disposable cuvettes (12.5 x 12.5 x 45 mm, Polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA), Brand). The measurement settings were set as followed:

Table 4.8: Measurement settings for DLS measurement.

Measurement settings	Values
Temperature	25 °C
Equilibration time	60 s
Number of measurements	6
Number of runs	10
Break time between repeated measurements	10 s
Properties of the test substance	
Material	nTiO ₂
Refraction index	2.7
Absorption coefficient	0.01
Dispersant	M9 medium
Refraction index	1.33620
Viscosity	0.8872

4.6.6 Zeta potential

The zeta (ζ) potential describes the electric potential of the surface of a moving particle in a suspension. It is not measurable directly, but it can be experimentally determined by measuring the electrophoretic mobility μ_e :

$$\mu_e = \frac{2}{3} * \frac{\varepsilon * \zeta * f(ka)}{\eta} \quad (4)$$

where ε describes the dielectric constant, $f(ka)$ the Henry function and η the viscosity.

The measurement was also performed using the Zetasizer Nano ZS, but for this setting, folded capillary zeta cells (Malvern, Polycarbonate with thin layers of gold, DTS1070) were used. The preparation followed the same procedure as for the DLS measurement (chapter 4.6.5)

Table 4.9: Measurement settings for zeta potential measurement.

Measurement settings	Values
Temperature	25 °C
Equilibration time	60 s
Number of measurements	6
Number of runs	10
Break time between repeated measurements	10 s
Properties of the test substance	
Material	nTiO ₂
Refraction index	2.7
Absorption coefficient	0.01
Dispersant	M9 medium
Refraction index	1.33620
Viscosity	0.8872
Attenuator	6
Voltage	50 V

4.6.7 Photocatalytic activity

Photocatalytic activity of NP suspensions was measured by degradation of methylene blue after exposure to UV light. In underlying process in detail: When UV-light hits the surface of a nTiO₂ particle, an electron-hole pair is generated. It then dissociates into a free electron and a free hole and migrates to the reactive surface. Both are transferred to an adsorbed molecule resulting in photodegradation (Nam et al., 2019) (Figure 4.6).

Figure 4.6: Schematic diagram of the photocatalytic process (Nam et al., 2019).

For this test, photocatalytic activity of nTiO₂ (40 mg/L) was tested in different preparations: with and without co-exposure with different Cd²⁺ concentrations (10 µg/L to 1 mg/L), after dark incubation and after irradiation, in ultra-pure water and in M9 medium. 4 mL of every suspension was prepared in glass petri dishes and left for 4 h in the dark to gain complete agglomeration. Then, methylene blue solution (12.5 mg/L) was added to each dish to achieve a 10% solution (v/v), and half of the samples were irradiated for 2 h at 231 W/m² (0.2 W/m² at 340 nm). All glass dishes were rotated on a roller mixer (Stuart, SRT1) at 50W. Absorbance of all preparations was measured at 0, 30, 60 and 120 min after illumination. For every measurement, 200 µL of the different solutions were pipetted into a 96 well plate (Costar 96 flat white), 4 replicates per sample. The absorbance was measured with a multimode reader (TECAN infinite200) at 633 nm.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

4.7 Molecular mode of action

In order to evaluate how the mixture of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ interacts with different structures inside the organism, three different tests were conducted. The measurement of the free intracellular calcium and the experiments on the membrane integrity were performed using *C. elegans*, while the cell viability assay was carried out with CHO-K1 cells.

Table 4.10: Overview of the different analytical methods, the used chemicals and their concentrations as well as the different organisms and test conditions.

Method	Chemicals	Organism	conditions
Measurement of free intracellular Ca ²⁺ with rhodamine	nTiO ₂ 40 mg/L Cd ²⁺ 1 mg/L NS8593 2,37 mg/L La ³⁺ 3.34 mg/L Heparin 0.4 mg/L	<i>C. elegans</i>	pH 7 dark and SSR
Measurement of membrane integrity with propidium iodide	nTiO ₂ 40 mg/L Cd ²⁺ 1 mg/L	<i>C. elegans</i>	pH 7 dark and SSR
Cell viability assay	nTiO ₂ 40 mg/L Cd ²⁺ 1 mg/L	CHO-K1 cells	pH 7 dark and SSR

4.7.1 Rhodamine test

The measurement of free intracellular calcium was performed according to Kawai et al. (1993), but instead of fura-2, Rhod-3 AM was used because it exhibits a large increase (> 2.5 fold) in fluorescence upon binding Ca^{2+} and very low fluorescence at rest (without Ca^{2+} binding). Rhod-3 AM, the acetoxymethyl ester of Rhod-3, is designed to penetrate readily into cells, and is hydrolysed to Rhod-3 by esterases in the living cell. Rhod-3 is the active, cell impermeant form which fluoresces upon Ca^{2+} binding (Molecular Probes, 2014).

The Loading Buffer was mixed by adding 20 μL PowerLoad concentrate (an optimized formulation of nonionic, Pluronic[®] surfactant polyols), 2 μL Rhod-3 (10 mM in DMSO) and 20 μL Probenecid (250 mM in PBS) to 2 mL M9 medium. After vortexing, the mixture was centrifuged for 2 minutes at 2000 g and transferred to a new tube. Nematodes from 3-day-old NGM-agar plates were rinsed off with 400 μL M9 medium and added to the mixture. After incubation for two hours at RT in the dark, the nematodes were filtered through 10 μm filter gaze and washed three times with M9 medium. 1 mL of the worm solution was pipetted in a 1.5 mL tube and centrifuged at 2000 g for 5 minutes. From each tube, 160 μL of the supernatant (control) and 160 μL of the pellet (test group with nematodes) were pipetted into a 96-well-plate (Costar 96 flat white). Each substance was tested with three replicates. The intracellular calcium concentration was measured fluorometrically (TECAN multimode reader infinite 200) with the settings shown in Table 4.11 using the pipette scheme shown in Table 4.12.

Materials and Methods

Table 4.11: Measurement settings for TECAN Multimode Reader Infinite 200.

Kinetic Cycles	155
Interval Time	Minimal
Mode	Fluorescence Top Reading
Excitation Wavelength	530 nm
Emission Wavelength	590 nm
Excitation Bandwidth	25 nm
Emission Bandwidth	20 nm
Gain	50
Number of Flashes	25
Integration Time	20 μ s
Lag Time	0 μ s
Settle Time	0 ms

Table 4.12: Pipette scheme of the first two rows of a 96-well-plate.

	Well number											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Control (supernatant)	ultra-pure H ₂ O			nTiO ₂ , 40 mg/L			Cd ²⁺ , 1 mg/L			nTiO ₂ , 40 mg/L + Cd ²⁺ , 1 mg/L		
Test (Pellet)	ultra-pure H ₂ O			nTiO ₂ , 40 mg/L			Cd ²⁺ , 1 mg/L			nTiO ₂ , 40 mg/L + Cd ²⁺ , 1 mg/L		

4.7.2 Membrane integrity

The evaluation whether the mixture of nTiO₂, Cd²⁺ and SSR affects the membrane integrity in the intestine of *C. elegans* was realised using propidium iodide (PI) as a red fluorescent dye which is not able to pass membranes and accordingly is used to detect dead cells in a population. PI intercalates with DNA bases without any sequence preference. When the dye is bound, the excitation/emission maxima shift from 493 / 636 nm to 535 / 617 nm and its fluorescence is enhanced 20- to 30-fold (Invitrogen, 2006).

Nematodes from 3-day-old agar plates were washed with M9 medium through a 10 µm filter gauze and were put in glass petri dishes. After two hours of starvation, the test solutions (nTiO₂ 40 mg/L and Cd²⁺ 1 mg/L) were added to the petri dishes and incubated for 90 mins in the dark or 60 mins dark and 30 mins SSR. Following this, a solution of PI (1 mg/mL) in ultrapure water was added to each test well and incubated for 5 minutes. Then, ten agile worms were sorted into each well of a 384-well plate (Corning Falcon® 384-well White Flat Bottom TC-treated) using an eyelash (Figure 4.6). The fluorescence was measured at excitation/emission wavelength of 533/617 nm (TECAN infinite pro). Additionally, the integrity of the intestinal membrane was checked under a microscope (Olympus BX40) using an MNG-filter module. Therefore, the remaining test organisms from the petri dishes were washed and put onto glass slides parallel to the TECAN measurement.

All optical measurements were analysed using the software *ImageJ* to compare the intensities of propidium iodide to calculate the effect of the single combinations under dark and illuminated conditions.

Figure 4.7: Pasteur pipette with an attached eyelash, used for sorting single nematodes.

4.7.3 Cell titer assay

The CellTiter-Fluor™ Cell Viability Assay is a fluorescence assay which is used to measure the relative number of viable cells in a colony. The principle is based on the measurement of the protease activity, which is only detectable at living cells and therefore a biomarker of cell viability. The activity is evaluated by measuring a peptide substrate which is fluorogenic and cell permeable. It consists of the amino acids Glycine and Phenylalanine (Gly-Phe-AFC). It can enter only intact cells and is cleaved by the protease, creating a fluorescent signal proportional to the number of living cells. (Promega, 2017)

The cell line used for this assay was Chinese hamster ovary (CHO) cells subtype K1. Two days in advance, the cells were washed twice with 10 mL PBS. After adding 1.5 mL 0.25% trypsin-EDTA (1X, gibco) and incubation at 37 °C for 5 min, the cells were detached from the bottom of the flask and mixed with 8.5 mL Ham's-F12 medium. To evaluate the amount of viable living cells, 25 µL of the suspension were mixed with 25 µL Blue Stain 0.1%. The measurement was performed using the Invitrogen Countess cell counter. The cell suspension was diluted to achieve a concentration of 100,000 cells/mL.

100 µL of the diluted cell suspension were pipetted in a 96 well plate (cellstar Greiner 655160) using a multipette, reaching a starting concentration of 10,000 cells/well. The well plates were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂.

The stock solutions of nTiO₂ (400 mg/L) and Cd²⁺ (10 mg/L) were prepared as described in chapter 4.3, diluted tenfold and incubated at 37 °C with constant shaking at 240 rpm for 10 min.

The Ham's-F12 medium was removed from the cells in the 96-well plate and 100 µL of each test solution is added. The well plates were incubated again for 24 h at 37 °C and 5% CO₂.

In order to prepare the assay reagent, 0.1 µL GF-ATC substrate (dissolved in DMSO) was added to 100 µL assay buffer (provided by Promega) and added to the test solutions in each well. After incubation at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ for 60 min, the fluorescence was measured (TECAN Infinite M200Pro).

Materials and Methods

Table 4.13: Parameter setting for the cell titer assay.

Parameter	Value
Excitation	390 nm
Emission	505 nm
Z-value	15.000
Gain	Optimal

4.8 Statistical analysis

The significance analysis of the experiments was calculated with the software Graph Pad Prism 9, using t-test, one-way or two-way ANOVA with Bonferroni post-test. Different number of replicates have been chosen depending on the type of test. All results are depicted as the means with the standard error. The range of the P value is between **** $P > 0.0001$ to not significant with $P > 0.9999$.

5 Chemical characterisation

5.1 Background

"Irradiation changes crystal structure, agglomeration size and relative element composition of agglomerates, leading to increased toxicity."

The hypothesis on the potential underlying process to explain the synergistic effect of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ under SSR focuses on the chemical properties of the mixture. Therefore, six different methods (Figure 4.2) were examined to characterise the chemical properties of nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-agglomerates. The experiments were either conducted with samples at two different pH values (4 and 7) with fixed concentrations of 40 mg/L nTiO₂ and 1 mg/L Cd²⁺ or with a specific nTiO₂ concentration (40 mg/L) and variable Cd²⁺ concentrations (10 µg/L to 10 mg/L) (Table 4.7). The intestine of *Caenorhabditis elegans* has a pH value of 4 (Chauhan et al., 2013), while the M9 medium is at pH 7. To simulate the transfer of particles from the pharynx (pH 7) to the intestine, these two values were chosen.

Figure 5.1: Flow chart of the analytical methods used to characterise the samples.

Chemical characterisation

Table 5.1: Overview of the different analytical methods, the used concentrations of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ and the different test conditions.

Method	[nTiO₂]	[Cd²⁺]	pH value	conditions
XRD	40 mg/L	1 mg/L	pH 4 and 7	dark and SSR
SEM	40 mg/L	1 mg/L	pH 4 and 7	dark and SSR
DLS	40 mg/L	10 µg/L to 10 mg/L	pH 7	dark and SSR
EDX	40 mg/L	1 mg/L	pH 4 and 7	dark and SSR
Zeta potential	40 mg/L	10 µg/L to 10 mg/L	pH 4 and 7	dark and SSR
Photocatalytic activity	40 mg/L	10 µg/L to 1 mg/L	pH 7	SSR

5.2 Results

5.2.1 Crystal structure

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used in order to study any changes in the crystal structure that may occur as a consequence of SSR exposure at different pH values (pH 4 dark and SSR, pH 7 dark and SSR) to mixtures of 40 mg/L nTiO₂ and 1 mg/L Cd²⁺. As nTiO₂ from Evonik Degussa (Aeroxide P25) consists of anatase and rutile at a ratio of 5:1 (Ohtani et al., 2010), their X-ray diffraction patterns were used for comparison in order to identify any unknown peaks (rutile standard: Powder Diffraction Standard, PDF card #21-1276; anatase standard: PDF card #21-1272).

Figure 5.2 shows the XRDs of the different samples. The peaks were identified at $2\theta = 27.5^\circ, 36.1^\circ, 39.2^\circ, 42.7^\circ, 44.1^\circ, 53.9^\circ$ and 56.5° , which match with the diffraction planes of rutile, while those located at $25.3^\circ, 37.0^\circ, 37.8^\circ, 38.5^\circ, 48.0^\circ, 53.3^\circ$ and 55.0° are assigned to the diffraction planes of anatase (Figure 5.2).

The crystal structure analysis shows that every sample is a mixture of crystalline rutile and anatase nTiO₂ with a composition of 86% anatase and 14% rutile. This was calculated by assigning the peaks to their crystal structure (anatase or rutile) and comparing the added intensities of the two patterns. This fits the bibliographical reference of the ratio (Gea et al., 2019).

Chemical characterisation

Figure 5.2: XRD patterns for the four different samples (pH 4 dark and SSR, pH 7 dark and SSR with $n=4$) in comparison to $n\text{TiO}_2$ rutile (PDF card #21-1276) and anatase standard (PDF card #21-1272).

5.2.2 Agglomeration size

The size of the $n\text{TiO}_2$ - Cd^{2+} - agglomerates was analysed with two different methods: Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and dynamic light scattering (DLS). The images of the Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM, Figure 5.3) show large agglomerates around 2 μm with no structural difference between pH 4 and 7 and neither between dark and irradiated conditions of $n\text{TiO}_2$ (40 mg/L) and Cd^{2+} (1 mg/L). This was a solely optical evaluation with no statistical analysis. For the exact size determination, dynamic light scattering was used.

Chemical characterisation

Figure 5.3: SEM images of the four different samples ($[nTiO_2] = 40 \text{ mg/L}$, $[Cd^{2+}] = 1 \text{ mg/L}$). A: pH 4 dark; B: pH 4 SSR; C: pH 7 dark and D: pH 7 SSR. E: one agglomerate at pH 4 SSR.

Using dynamic light scattering (DLS, Figure 5.4), combinations with Cd^{2+} concentrations from $10 \mu\text{g/L}$ to 10 mg/L in combination with $nTiO_2$ but only at pH 7 were tested. The experiments with samples at pH 4 were considered obsolete, because the formation of agglomerates takes place in the aquatic environment before ingestion. The test shows

similar results regarding the average size as the SEM: pure nTiO₂ agglomerates have an average size of 2600 nm in the dark, while SSR-treated nTiO₂ agglomerates are approximately 15% smaller (2100 nm). When combined with low Cd²⁺ concentrations (10 and 50 µg/L), not illuminated samples are significantly larger than the ones exposed to SSR. At 100 and 500 µg/L Cd²⁺, the size is nearly equal with no significant difference, and at 1, 5 and 10 mg/L, all SSR-treated samples show higher agglomeration sizes than the dark ones, but only in combination with 1 mg/L cadmium, there is a significant difference between dark and SSR (Figure 5.4). To visualise the trend between the different concentrations in percent, all values measured in the dark were deducted from those under SSR (Figure 5.5). The percental difference is negative for Cd²⁺ concentrations up to 500 µg/L and at the minimum for solely nTiO₂ with -18.61%. At [Cd²⁺] = 1 mg/L, the maximum is achieved with 16.06%, higher concentrations lead to a decrease to 11.14% ([Cd²⁺] = 5 mg/L) and 7.99% ([Cd²⁺] = 10 mg/L).

Figure 5.4: DLS measurement of nTiO₂ agglomeration size with and without addition of different Cd²⁺ concentrations. Depicted are the means with the standard errors. Significance of deviations are shown with **** $P \leq 0.0001$ and ** $P \leq 0.01$ with $n=6$.

Chemical characterisation

Figure 5.5: Percental difference of the values when all mean values measured in the dark are deducted from those under SSR.

Comparing the significance of the different Cd²⁺ concentrations under dark conditions, all samples containing cadmium are significantly different from pure nTiO₂, and a Cd²⁺ concentration of 5 mg/L is significantly different from smaller Cd²⁺ concentrations (Table 5.2). Under irradiated conditions, there is a significant difference between 10, 50, 100 µg/L and 5 mg/L to pure nTiO₂, and 1 mg/L Cd²⁺ to concentrations up to 100 µg/L. Under irradiation, 5 mg/L of Cd²⁺ is only significant different from 0 and 500 µg/L and 1 mg/L of Cd²⁺ (Table 5.3).

Chemical characterisation

Table 5.2: Statistical analysis with Bonferroni post-test regarding size differences of nTiO₂ agglomerates, when complemented with different cadmium concentrations under dark conditions.

[Cd ²⁺]	0 µg/L	10 µg/L	50 µg/L	100 µg/L	500 µg/L	1 mg/L	5 mg/L	10 mg/L
0 µg/L	-	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
10 µg/L	< 0.0001	-	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	0.0023	< 0.0001	0.0016
50 µg/L	< 0.0001	> 0.9999	-	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	0.0048	< 0.0001	0.0036
100 µg/L	< 0.0001	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	-	> 0.9999	0.3698	0.0003	0.3372
500 µg/L	< 0.0001	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	-	0.0018	< 0.0001	0.0012
1 mg/L	< 0.0001	0.0023	0.0048	0.3698	0.0018	-	0.8794	> 0.9999
5 mg/L	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.0003	< 0.0001	0.8794	-	0.5538
10 mg/L	< 0.0001	0.0016	0.0036	0.3372	0.0012	> 0.9999	0.5538	-

Table 5.3: Statistical analysis with Bonferroni post-test regarding size differences of nTiO₂ agglomerates, when complemented with different Cd concentrations under irradiated conditions.

[Cd ²⁺]	0 µg/L	10 µg/L	50 µg/L	100 µg/L	500 µg/L	1 mg/L	5 mg/L	10 mg/L
0 µg/L	-	< 0.0001	0.0029	0.0021	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	0.0003	0.1599
10 µg/L	< 0.0001	-	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	0.0009	< 0.0001	> 0.9999	0.0574
50 µg/L	0.0029	> 0.9999	-	> 0.9999	0.1797	< 0.0001	> 0.9999	> 0.9999
100 µg/L	0.0021	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	-	0.1343	< 0.0001	> 0.9999	> 0.9999
500 µg/L	> 0.9999	0.0009	0.1797	0.1343	-	0.0539	0.0189	> 0.9999
1 mg/L	> 0.9999	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.0539	-	< 0.0001	0.0011
5 mg/L	0.0003	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	0.0189	< 0.0001	-	0.6425
10 mg/L	0.1599	0.0574	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	0.0011	0.6425	-

The size distribution (Figure 5.6) shows that nearly all samples vary in the range between 1000 and 2000 nm by at least 10%. Concerning all conditions, the tendency of the average agglomeration size is decreasing distinctly, which is also shown in Figure 5.4. The variability of the size of the nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-agglomerates is higher at dark than at illuminated conditions, while the smallest range of size is at nTiO₂ with 500 µg/L Cd²⁺ under SSR.

Size Distribution

Figure 5.6: Comparison of size distribution of nanoparticles in different experimental set-ups, combining light/no-light exposure with different Cd²⁺-additions to nTiO₂ (40 mg/L).

5.2.3 Element composition

Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was used to determine the elemental composition of $n\text{TiO}_2\text{-Cd}^{2+}$ -agglomerates under dark and irradiated conditions and shows an average percental amount of the single elements in the four different samples (pH 4 and 7, dark and SSR, Table 5.4). Each measurement was replicated four times at different local positions of the $n\text{TiO}_2\text{-Cd}^{2+}$ -crystal. With the obtained percental values, the mean value was calculated for each element in each sample: green for titanium (Ti), blue for oxygen (O) and red for cadmium (Cd). To put the percental values in a comparable ratio, the mean of Ti was set to 1, resulting in four different relations: comparing pH 4 dark and SSR, the amount of oxygen slightly differs from 2.9047 to 2.3304, while cadmium stays nearly the same (0.0006 at dark to 0.0007 at irradiated conditions). At pH 7, oxygen also decreases from dark (3.4347) to SSR (3.0425) and cadmium increases from 0.0014 (dark) to 0.0019 (SSR). But the main difference is detectable when focussing on the influence of pH: At pH 7, the relative Cd^{2+} content is more than twice as high as at pH 4: it differs from 0.0006 to 0.0014 at dark and from 0.0007 to 0.0019 at irradiated conditions.

Table 5.4: EDX results of the four different samples with 16 technical measurements of each sample. All values are percentages at four different sampling positions, with an average value for titanium (green), oxygen (blue) and cadmium (Cd).

Sample A pH 4 dark				Sample B pH 4 SSR			
	Ti	O	Cd		Ti	O	Cd
[%]	30.58	69.41	0.02	[%]	38.17	61.81	0.02
	20.75	79.24	0.01		31.03	68.95	0.02
	21.16	78.84	0.00		25.57	74.41	0.02
	29.94	70.04	0.03		25.31	74.67	0.02
	25.61	74.38	0.02		30.02	69.96	0.02
ratio	1.0000	2.9047	0.0006	ratio	1.0000	2.3304	0.0007
Sample C pH 7 dark				Sample D pH 7 SSR			
	Ti	O	Cd		Ti	O	Cd
[%]	22.28	77.57	0.15	[%]	28.14	71.68	0.18
	24.51	75.33	0.15		18.97	80.88	0.15
	22.22	77.69	0.06		26.14	73.68	0.19
	21.08	78.84	0.08		25.56	74.39	0.05
	22.52	77.36	0.11		24.70	75.16	0.14
ratio	1.0000	3.4347	0.0014	ratio	1.0000	3.0425	0.0019

Chemical characterisation

The statistical analysis using a Bonferroni Multiple Comparison Test shows no significant differences in the elemental distribution of the different samples with regard to Ti and O (Table 9.1 and Table 9.2 Annex), but concerning Cd (Table 5.5): while there is no significant difference between samples A and B (pH 4) or C and D (pH 7), the combinations A vs C, A vs D, B vs C and B vs D are significantly different (**P ≤ 0.01 and *P ≤ 0.05).

Table 5.5: Statistical analysis of the four different samples considering cadmium (**P ≤ 0.01 and *P ≤ 0.05).

Bonferroni's Multiple Comparison Test	Significant? P < 0,05?	Summary
<i>Cd A vs Cd B</i>	No	ns
<i>Cd A vs Cd C</i>	Yes	*
<i>Cd A vs Cd D</i>	Yes	**
<i>Cd B vs Cd C</i>	Yes	*
<i>Cd B vs Cd D</i>	Yes	**
<i>Cd C vs Cd D</i>	No	ns

That leads to the conclusion that the proton concentration (pH value) of the surrounding media is decisive for the agglomeration composition. The solubility of Cd²⁺ increases with decreasing pH value (Kayser, 2020). In combination with nTiO₂, that means that the adsorption of Cd²⁺ ions is stronger with higher pH values (Gao et al., 2004, Haq et al., 2018). Kumar et al. (2021) used the photocatalytic activity of nTiO₂ to bind Cd²⁺ under simulated solar radiation, leading to an adsorption capacity of 82.8% at pH 7.2 and 88.2% at pH 10. The conclusion of these results leads to the assumption of a reversible binding situation between Cd²⁺ and nTiO₂, as already suggested at the results of the crystal structure analysis (Chapter 5.2.1).

So different pH values have an influence on the amount of Cd²⁺ in the agglomerates. This can be transferred to the uptake of nTiO₂- Cd²⁺-agglomerates by *C. elegans*: Where the pH value is at pH 7 in the pharynx, it decreases within the intestine continuously to a pH value of 4 (Chauhan et al., 2013). That means that during the passage from mouth to anus, the agglomerates pass through a pH value drop, which leads to the detachment of

cadmium ions from nTiO₂. If and how the availability of free Cd²⁺ ions affect the cells of *C. elegans* will be discussed in chapter 6.

5.2.4 Zeta potential

The degree of repulsion determines the agglomeration behaviour of the particles. The repulsion is directly linked to the surface charge, which can be determined by measuring the zeta potential. This experiment was conducted to see whether SSR or different Cd²⁺ concentrations (10 µg/L to 10 mg/L) have any impact on the surface charge of the nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-agglomerates.

Testing the surface charge of single nTiO₂ (40 mg/L) and in combination with different Cd²⁺ concentrations (10 µg/L to 10 mg/L), no significant changes between the different samples at the same pH value were detected (Figure 5.7). The values at pH 4 range from -16.3 mV to -18.4 mV, at pH 7 from -18.3 mV up to -20.7 mV (

Table 5.6).

Comparing the agglomerates considering the change in the pH value from 4 to 7 (Figure 5.8), seven samples show significant changes in the zeta potential from 1.63 – 2.94 mV difference. Only at a Cd²⁺ concentration of 5 mg/L, no significance is detected.

Table 5.6: Mean zeta potential values of single nTiO₂ and in combination with different Cd²⁺ concentrations from 10 µg/L to 10 mg/L.

Mean values [mV]	pH 7		pH 4	
	dark	SSR	dark	SSR
nTiO ₂ (40 mg/L)	-19.7	-19.5	-17.9	-17.4
+ Cd ²⁺ (10 µg/L)	-20.3	-20.7	-17.4	-17.7
+ Cd ²⁺ (50 µg/L)	-19.4	-19.3	-17.3	-17.2
+ Cd ²⁺ (100 µg/L)	-19.8	-19.2	-16.7	-16.3
+ Cd ²⁺ (500 µg/L)	-20.0	-20.0	-18.2	-17.0
+ Cd ²⁺ (1 mg/L)	-19.1	-19.1	-18.4	-16.5
+ Cd ²⁺ (5 mg/L)	-18.8	-18.3	-16.9	-18.1
+ Cd ²⁺ (10 mg/L)	-19.1	-19.4	-17.3	-16.8

Chemical characterisation

Figure 5.7: Zeta potential with different Cd²⁺-concentrations at pH 4 and 7 under dark and irradiated conditions to show the general significance between the pH values but not between dark and SSR.

Figure 5.8: Comparison between pH 7 and pH 4 of the zeta potential, dark and SSR values of each concentration were combined (****P < 0.0001, ***P < 0.005 and **P < 0.005).

5.2.5 Photocatalytic activity

The photocatalytic activity of a substance is a marker for interactions with surrounding structures, for example with membranes or tissues (Parra-Ortiz 2022). An increase of photocatalytic activity of nTiO₂ could - following the formulated hypothesis - lead to an increased formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), resulting in a damaged membrane integrity. It is measured within an absorption experiment, which correlates conversely to the photocatalytic activity.

Comparing the absorption of pure nTiO₂ (40 mg/L) and in combination with different Cd²⁺ concentrations (10 - 1000 µg/L) over time in M9 medium, all starting values at t = 0 minutes were set to 1, resulting in a normalised absorption (Figure 5.9). After 60 minutes of SSR, the absorption is decreased for all Cd²⁺ concentrations compared to pure nTiO₂ (grey), while especially higher concentrations such as 500 or 1000 µg/L show the lowest absorption. After 120 minutes, the normalised absorption of every sample is decreased, and concentration-dependent influences are visible. At this point of time, nearly every Cd²⁺ concentration shows higher absorption than nTiO₂ except 25, 50 and 500 µg/L.

To visualise the concentration-dependency, all normalised absorption values are plotted against the Cd²⁺ concentration after 60 (green) and 120 minutes (blue) of irradiation compared to pure nTiO₂ (ticked green and blue line) (Figure 5.10). This figure is chosen to point out the concentration-dependent trend in comparison to pure nTiO₂. As described before, there is a decrease in absorption after 60 minutes for every concentration combination compared to pure nTiO₂, while at 120 minutes, there is only a decreasing effect at combinations of nTiO₂ with 50, 75 and 500 µg/L Cd²⁺.

Chemical characterisation

Figure 5.9: Normalised absorption units of pure nTiO₂ (40 mg/L) and in combination with different Cd²⁺ concentrations after 0, 60 and 120 minutes of irradiation.

Chemical characterisation

Figure 5.10: Concentration-dependency of the absorption from nTiO₂ (40 mg/L) in combination with different Cd²⁺ concentrations compared to pure nTiO₂ (40 mg/L) after 60 and 120 minutes of SSR incubation.

5.3 Discussion

The different methodological approaches used for the chemical analysis addressed the crystal structure, size, element composition, and surface charge as well as photocatalytic properties and showed different results.

5.3.1 Crystal structure

The change of the crystal structure would be detected by visible shifts in the crystal pattern, which are an indicator for the incorporation of Cd^{2+} by nTiO_2 or the influence of 30 minutes of simulated solar radiation. But the XRD analysis showed no difference between the samples. Therefore, it can be assumed that Cd^{2+} connects only statistically to nTiO_2 but does not change the crystal structure. This leads to the assumption of ionic interactions and excludes the formation of a covalent bond which would change the crystal pattern: In principle, the X-rays get diffracted by the inter-atomic spacing in the crystal. By forming covalent bonds between nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} , this spacing would be changed and therefore would result in a different pattern (Krischner and Koppelhuber-Bitschnau, 1994). Subsequently, it can be assumed, that the bond between nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} is reversible and restricted to the surface forming a monolayer. This is in line with the description of a Langmuir isotherm of adsorption, which is not visible in XRD and must be checked with other methods. Langmuir (1916) described the quantification of the adsorption capacity q with the following equation (5):

$$q = \frac{b \cdot q_m \cdot C}{1 + b \cdot C} \quad (5)$$

with b for the adsorption energy sorption constant, C for the metal concentration in solution and q_m for the solid maximum adsorption capacity. Engates and Shipley (2011) measured the Langmuir parameters for nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} : $q_m = 135.14 \mu\text{mol/g}$ and $b = 74.00 \text{ L/mol}$. This model for the interaction between nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} was confirmed by experiments of Haq et al. (2018), Samet (2017b) and Engates and Shipley (2011). Likewise, irradiation does not disturb the crystal pattern of the agglomerates either.

5.3.2 Agglomeration size

Considering only the results of the SEM, it seems that neither simulated solar radiation nor the pH value has any impact on the size of nTiO_2 - Cd^{2+} - agglomerates. These measurements are only visual on-spot observations, which cannot detect the differences shown in the DLS measurement. In addition to that, SEM measurements include a fixed cadmium concentration of 1 mg/L, so a broader range of Cd^{2+} concentrations was not included.

The DLS results lead to the conclusion that the amount of cadmium ions in the samples plays a crucial role in size and composition of the agglomerates at pH 7.

The Cd^{2+} concentration seems to have a decisive effect on the agglomeration size and behaviour under irradiation: there is an increase in agglomeration size from 10 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 1 mg/L Cd^{2+} . Smaller concentrations (up to 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$) inhibit the formation of larger agglomerates, while higher concentrations enlarge the agglomeration size compared to dark conditions. Under SSR, the surface of particles like nTiO_2 can be positively charged, and the emerging electrons resulting from that photolysis can induce redox reactions with surrounding cations (Stevanovic et al., 2012). In this case, Cd^{2+} ions are reduced and can either form elementary cadmium or react with oxygen, forming CdO (Naqvi et al., 2021). The formation of cadmium oxide (CdO) takes place directly on the surface of nTiO_2 , and referring to the gained results, it is the more likely mode of action: with increasing Cd^{2+} concentrations, more CdO-molecules develop and increase the agglomeration size. In order to prove that theory, future experiments could consider measuring CdO. This effect is supported by the DLVO theory: this theory (named after Derjaguin, Landau, Verwey and Overbeek (van Oss, 2008)) models the stability of colloidal systems. It is based on the interaction of repulsion and attraction of dispersed particles in a suspension and can be described as the sum of attractive van-der-Waals forces and electrostatic repulsion forces at the electric double layer (Derjaguin and Landau, 1941). When particles form colloids in an ionic strength surrounding, the ions adhere on the particle's surface and compress the electric double layer as well as the surface charge. This lowers the repulsion energy and promote attractive forces, leading to an increase in agglomeration and therefore in particle size. Especially divalent cations

like Cd^{2+} interfere with the double layer, so by increasing the Cd^{2+} concentration, larger $\text{nTiO}_2\text{-Cd}^{2+}$ - agglomerates are formed (Derjaguin and Landau, 1941, van Oss, 2008).

The acid-base behaviour of nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} changes with different pH values. At pH 7, Gao et al. (2004) proposed the following redox reaction:

The cadmium ions are linked *via* the oxygen to titanium and form ionic bonds. At a Cd^{2+} concentration of 1 mg/L, a saturation is achieved and the size evolves back (Gao et al., 2004).

At dark conditions, the size decreases with increasing Cd^{2+} concentration, but there are only significant differences at a Cd^{2+} concentration of 5 and 10 mg/L in the dark. That can be explained by an “overload” of Cd^{2+} ions on nTiO_2 , the surface is saturated and the nTiO_2 particles cannot absorb more than a specific amount of cadmium due to their specific surface area (Gao et al., 2004). That also explains the larger variability in size under dark conditions (Figure 5.6).

5.3.3 Element composition

The result of the EDX analysis leads to the conclusion that the proton concentration (pH value) of the surrounding media is decisive for the element composition. It is known that the solubility of Cd^{2+} increases with decreasing pH value (Kayser, 2020). In combination with nTiO_2 , that means that the adsorption of Cd^{2+} ions is stronger with higher pH values (Gao et al., 2004, Haq et al., 2018). Kumar et al. (2021) used the photocatalytic activity of nTiO_2 to bind Cd^{2+} under simulated solar radiation, leading to an adsorption capacity of 82.8% at pH 7.2 and 88.2% at pH 10. The conclusion of these results leads to the assumption of a reversible binding situation between Cd^{2+} and nTiO_2 , as already suggested at the results of the crystal structure analysis (Chapter 5.2.1).

So different pH values have an influence on the amount of Cd^{2+} in the agglomerates. This can be transferred to the uptake of $\text{nTiO}_2\text{-Cd}^{2+}$ -agglomerates by *C. elegans*: Where the pH value is at pH 7 in the pharynx, it decreases within the intestine continuously to a pH value of 4 (Chauhan et al., 2013). That means that during the passage from mouth to anus, the agglomerates pass through a pH value drop, which leads to the detachment of

cadmium ions from nTiO₂. If and how the availability of free Cd²⁺ ions affect the cells of *C. elegans* will be discussed in chapter 6.

5.3.4 Zeta potential

The zeta potential is only pH-dependent, neither irradiation conditions nor Cd²⁺ concentration have any impact on the charge. If the absolute value of the zeta potential decreases, it means that the interparticle repellent forces are reduced and this leads to amplified agglomeration (Wang et al., 2018). Exceeding the threshold values of ± 30 mV, no agglomeration occurs (Nia et al., 2015). In the case of nTiO₂- Cd²⁺-agglomerates, pH 7 leads to a decreased surface charge because of the higher adsorption of Cd²⁺ onto the surface of nTiO₂. This pH-value dependency correlates with the results from the EDX measurements (chapter 5.2.3).

The equilibrium (point of zero charge, PZC) of nTiO₂ P25 particles is at pH 6.8 (Xie and Gao, 2009), which is close to the set pH value of M9 medium. At this point, two different adsorption processes can take place: chemisorption and physisorption (Figure 5.11). Chemisorption is a special form of adsorption in which the adsorbate is bound to the adsorbent (substrate) by stronger chemical bonds. Chemisorption chemically changes the adsorbate and/or the adsorbent and is pH- dependent. Physisorption refers to the process of physical adsorption, in which an adsorbed molecule is bound to a substrate only by physical forces (Xie and Gao, 2009).

a) chemisorption

b) physisorption

Figure 5.11: The adsorption process describing two different mode of actions: (a) chemisorption, where the adsorption progress is dependent on the pH value and the point of zero charge (PZC). (b) Physisorption (adapted from Xie and Gao (2009) using their initial theory where Cd²⁺ was applied as the metal).

Related to the results from the zeta potential measurements, chemisorption is the more likely mode of action because a pH-dependency was observed.

Following the DLVO theory (chapter 5.2.2), the surface charge should also be influenced by the Cd^{2+} concentration: the positive charged Cd^{2+} ions form two layers around the negative particles (in this case related to oxide anions), which lead to a repulsion towards other particles with this double layer. The thickness is usually dependent upon the type and concentration of the positive ions in the solution. This results in a change of the electric potential, which is related to the mobility of the particles, the zeta potential (Zeta-Meter, 2022). But the conducted experiments give no indication of such concentration dependency, which – at this point – is not explainable.

5.3.5 Photocatalytic activity

Higher absorption values are equivalent to a decreasing photocatalytic activity. In this experiment, the absorption of methylene blue in combination with pure nTiO_2 and combinations of nTiO_2 with Cd^{2+} at different concentrations is measured. In order to prove that pure nTiO_2 is photocatalytic active, the absorption should decrease over time, which is visible after 120 minutes, but not after 60 minutes. The reason for that increase after 60 minutes could be the charge separation of electrons between nTiO_2 and the different cations in M9 medium, leading to a temporary increase, which is a common observed effect in photocatalysts such as nTiO_2 (Lewis, 1998, Kelly et al., 1999). The cations of the surrounding media compete with nTiO_2 and the photocatalytic dye for the light-induced emerge of an electron from the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) of nTiO_2 and making a reverse reaction improbable. Adding more cations such as Cd^{2+} , this effect is enhanced and explains the high decrease of the absorption after 60 minutes. Thus, the photocatalytic activity is also intensified. Especially, this phenomenon is visible for high concentrated Cd^{2+} combinations such as 500 and 1000 $\mu\text{g/L}$. This effect is different after 120 minutes: just for concentrations of 25, 75 and 500 $\mu\text{g/L}$, the photocatalytic activity of nTiO_2 is increased, while it is inhibited at all other Cd^{2+} concentrations. The inhibiting effect could be explained by the theory of hole trapping: the emerging electrons leave a hole in the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) of nTiO_2 , and due to the disturbed reverse reaction, it is not filled again. The result is that nTiO_2 loads up on these holes and loses its photocatalytic property after an amount of time (Rajh et al., 1999). At Cd^{2+} concentrations of 75 and 1000 $\mu\text{g/L}$, this effect

Chemical characterisation

is the most recognisable, because they have the highest effect after 60 minutes, but the lowest after 120 minutes.

This experiment shows that the photocatalytic activity is essentially influenced by the Cd^{2+} concentration – as observed also regarding the agglomeration size (Chapter 5.2.2).

6 Molecular mode of action

6.1 Background

To evaluate the mode of action, three different analytical methods were conducted (Figure 6.1) testing three different hypotheses.

Figure 6.1: Flow chart of the analytical methods used to evaluate the possible mode of action.

“Gon-2 calcium ion channels play a relevant role in the synergistic inhibitory effect of nTiO₂- Cd²⁺-mixtures under simulated solar radiation.”

The first hypothesis is based on the reproduction inhibition of 80% observed in *C. elegans* by Samet (2017b). *Gon-2* is a calcium ion channel which is expressed predominantly in the intestine of *C. elegans* (Teramoto et al., 2005) and regulates the development of the gonads (Church and Lambie, 2003). A sequence blast conducted by Lambie et al. (2015) showed that it is comparable with the human TRPM7 channel. Calcium as a second messenger is very important also for the self-defence of cells: when a toxic substance (such as cadmium) attacks the cell, often the intracellular calcium concentration is increased (Figure 6.2). If this mechanism is disturbed, the cell loses this defence mechanism and is vulnerable to toxic substances (Kawaii et al., 1993, Berridge et al., 2000, Cerella et al., 2010).

Molecular mode of action

Figure 6.2: The Ca^{2+} signalling network. If a stimulus hits the cell, Ca^{2+} -mobilising signals are generated, which can trigger an increase in intracellular calcium concentration, which then can trigger various Ca^{2+} sensitive processes. It can be terminated by the OFF-mechanisms and restore a resting level of Ca^{2+} (adapted from Berridge et al. (2000)).

To verify that hypothesis, a known human TRPM7-antagonist called NS8593 was used which should also work for *Gon-2* because of the similarities in the sequences of TRPM7 and *Gon-2*. Chubanov and Gudermann (2020) have studied the binding situation of NS8593 to the TRPM7 receptor. They describe it as a negative gating modulator that causes the receptor to close and prevents calcium ions from leaving the cell.

The intracellular calcium concentration under dark conditions and SSR was tested using rhodamine as a fluorescent dye.

If the mixture of nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} blocks *Gon-2* calcium ion channels, the combination of nTiO_2 and NS8593 should show the same effects under SSR on intracellular calcium concentration and was therefore used for comparison.

“The photocatalytic activity of nTiO_2 damages the integrity of intestinal membranes in *C. elegans*.”

To investigate the second hypothesis, the adult worms were incubated for four hours with different solutions of M9 medium, nTiO_2 , Cd^{2+} and their combination under dark and irradiated (30 minutes of SSR) conditions. Afterwards, they were analysed microscopically using propidium iodide as a fluorescent dye, which shows fluorescent intensity dependent on the number of damaged cells (Invitrogen, 2006).

“The effect of the mixture under simulated solar radiation on cells like CHO is comparable to those on *C. elegans*, which would describe a toxicodynamic effect.”

To investigate the assumed effect on single cells, and to gain a more detailed insight of the specific mode of action, a cell viability assay with Chinese hamster ovary (CHO-K1) cells was conducted. The principle of this test is based on the interaction of living cells with a live-cell protease, and the inhibition of the activity is proportional to the number of dead cells in the mixture. As a positive control, digitonin with a concentration of 14.68 µg/mL (EC₅₀) was used. Digitonin is a known cell toxin and therefore a valid criterion for this test. M9 medium (10 vol% in ultra-pure water) conducts as the negative control. The concentrations of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ are the same used in previous experiments to gain complete comparability (nTiO₂ = 40 mg/L, Cd²⁺ = 1 mg/L).

6.2 Results

6.2.1 The role of free intracellular calcium

All samples (solely nTiO₂, Cd²⁺ and NS8593 as well as their combinations) were tested under dark and irradiated conditions (30 minutes of SSR) on adult *C. elegans*. The control does not show any effect in the dark (normalised rhodamine intensity of 1; Figure 6.3), under SSR it is a little bit higher with a normalised intensity of 3 (Figure 6.4). Single nTiO₂ also shows no effect in the dark (Figure 6.3) but decreases after 30 minutes of SSR (Figure 6.4). Cd²⁺ alone increases intracellular calcium levels under dark conditions and under SSR significantly in every measurement. The combination of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ decreases the intracellular calcium concentration only under SSR, but not under dark conditions (Figure 6.3).

Adding NS8593, single exposure shows a small increase in intensity, but no detectable effect. Combined with Cd²⁺, it leads to an increase in the intensity at both conditions. The mixture of NS8593 and nTiO₂ shows the same effect as the combination of TiO₂ and Cd²⁺: under dark conditions, there is no change compared to single exposure, but under irradiation, the intensity decreases noticeably (Figure 6.3 and Figure 6.4).

Molecular mode of action

dark conditions

Figure 6.3: Fluorescence intensity of rhodamine (F/F0) in intestinal cells of adult *C. elegans* under dark conditions at pH 7 and 20 °C with n=3. Concentrations of 40 mg/L nTiO₂, 1 mg/L Cd²⁺ and 2,37 mg/L NS8593 were used.

irradiated conditions

Figure 6.4: Fluorescence intensity of rhodamine (F/F0) in intestinal cells of adult *C. elegans* under irradiated conditions at pH 7 and 20 °C with n=3. Concentrations of 40 mg/L nTiO₂, 1 mg/L Cd²⁺ and 2,37 mg/L NS8593 were used.

For further verification, two additional substances were tested: Lanthanum ions (La³⁺) and Heparin (Hep). These interact with different ion channels: La³⁺ blocks the TRPM3-like receptor GTL-1 (Xiao and Xu, 2009) and Hep is an antagonist of the IP₃-receptor ITR-

Molecular mode of action

1 (Saleem et al., 2014). Both receptors are also located in the intestine of *C. elegans* (Teramoto et al., 2005, Walker et al., 2004). A rhodamine test with all three antagonists was performed (Figure 6.5):

Figure 6.5: Fluorescence intensity of rhodamine (F/F_0) in intestinal cells of adult *C. elegans* under SSR at pH 7 and 20 °C with $n=3$. Concentrations of 40 mg/L nTiO_2 , 1 mg/L Cd^{2+} , 2,37 mg/L NS8593, 3.34 mg/L La^{3+} and 0.4 mg/L Hep were used.

This experiment shows a completely different result as the ones before. Single nTiO_2 is below the combinations with Cd^{2+} and NS8593, and all substances show an increase in fluorescence compared to the control except single Cd^{2+} . The intensity of the substances NS8593, Hep and La^{3+} are below single nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} , but their combination with nTiO_2 lead to an increase compared to the combination of nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} . Comparing the different substances, the intensity increases from $\text{La}^{3+} > \text{Hep} > \text{NS8593}$.

6.2.2 Membrane integrity

Under dark conditions, there is no detectable difference between the control and the substances. Independent of the chemical exposure of the sample, no optical measurement shows an increase in fluorescence (Figure 6.6).

Figure 6.6: Measurement of membrane integrity of adult *C. elegans* at dark conditions of the control (A), single nTiO₂ (B), Cd²⁺ (C) and the combination of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ (D) after 4 hours of incubation at 20 °C and staining with propidium iodide.

In most of the replica, there is an increased fluorescence when measuring the nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-combination under SSR compared to the other samples (Figure 6.7). This supports the hypothesis that the photocatalytic activity of nTiO₂ damages the cell membrane tremendously, so that toxic agents such as Cd²⁺ can harm the cell. This can also explain the decrease in intracellular calcium levels (Chapter 6.2.1). As shown in Figure 6.7 D, the effect of membrane damage is mainly observed in the pharynx and beginning intestine of *C. elegans*.

Molecular mode of action

Figure 6.7: Measurement of membrane integrity of adult *C. elegans* at irradiated conditions of the control (A), single nTiO₂ (B), Cd²⁺ (C) and the combination of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ (D) after 4 hours of incubation at 20 °C, including 30 minutes of SSR, and staining with propidium iodide.

In most of the replica, there is an increased fluorescence when measuring the nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-combination under SSR compared to the other samples (Figure 6.7). This supports the hypothesis that the photocatalytic activity of nTiO₂ damages the cell membrane tremendously, so that toxic agents such as Cd²⁺ can harm the cell. This can also explain the decrease in intracellular calcium levels (Chapter 6.2.1). As shown in Figure 6.7 D, the effect of membrane damage is mainly observed in the pharynx and beginning intestine of *C. elegans*.

In addition to the optical measurement, different approaches of quantification are tested. The sorting of worms into a 382-well-plate, followed by an absorbance measurement does not lead to quantifiable results because the background was too high to measure single worms in the propidium iodide solution. To get an impression if the observed differences are reliable, all experimental images are analysed with the software ImageJ which calculates the number of fluorescent pixels in a defined area.

Molecular mode of action

The focus of this experiment lies in the effect of nTiO₂ with and without cadmium ions relating to the control, so not every experiment was conducted with worms treated with single Cd²⁺ ions. The analysis of the samples under dark conditions showed no significant change in the three experiments (Figure 6.8).

Figure 6.8: Intensity of the single samples under dark conditions at three different tests with adult *C. elegans*, each intensity was calculated with 20 replicates, after 4 hours of incubation at 20 °C and staining with propidium iodide.

To check whether the optical difference between the combination of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ in relation to single nTiO₂ and single Cd²⁺ under SSR is also quantifiable, the percentual difference of the main values were calculated (Figure 6.9): The intensity of single nTiO₂ is by 52.64 ± 43.71% higher than the control, single Cd²⁺ only by 38.22 ± 118.91% and the combination by 250.45 ± 211.20%. But the high standard deviation shows that the single experiments cannot easily be summarised in one value, but every experiment should be evaluated separately.

Molecular mode of action

Figure 6.9: Box plot diagram of the intensity of the samples relative to the control under irradiated conditions with adult *C. elegans*; mean values + SEM of the six experiments described in Figure 6.10 after 4 hours of incubation at 20 °C, including 30 minutes of SSR, and staining with propidium iodide.

As shown in Figure 6.10 and Table 6.1, the intensity of the combination of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ under irradiated conditions is significantly higher than the control, solely nTiO₂ or solely Cd²⁺. SSR should not have any impact on cadmium-treated worms. Therefore, the measurement of Cd²⁺ was only performed in the first three measurements to exclude any effect of solely cadmium ions. The statistical analysis using a 2-way ANOVA (Table 6.1) confirmed in five of six experiments that the combination has a significant impact on the membrane structure of *C. elegans*, while there is no significant difference between control and solely nTiO₂. Figure 6.10 shows the consistently increased intensity of the combination compared to the individual substances.

Molecular mode of action

Membrane Integrity under SSR

Figure 6.10: Intensity of the single samples under irradiated conditions at six different tests with adult *C. elegans*, each intensity was calculated with 20 replicates, after 4 hours of incubation at 20 °C, including 30 minutes of SSR, and staining with propidium iodide.

Table 6.1: Bonferroni's multiple comparison of the control vs nTiO₂ vs nTiO₂ + Cd²⁺ vs Cd²⁺ under irradiated conditions for the six conducted experiments.

	1	2	3	4	5	6
control vs. nTiO ₂ (40 mg/L)	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	0.1357	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	> 0.9999
Control vs. nTiO ₂ (40 mg/L) + Cd ²⁺ (1 mg/L)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.0313	0.0525
nTiO ₂ (40 mg/L) vs. nTiO ₂ (40 mg/L) + Cd ²⁺ (1 mg/L)	0.0008	0.0002	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.0330	0.3552
control vs. Cd ²⁺ (1 mg/L)	> 0.9999	> 0.9999	0.1498			

6.2.3 Cell viability

Figure 6.11 describes the difference between the single exposures and the combination under dark and irradiated conditions. It is noticeable that SSR has no impact on the inhibition activity of Cd^{2+} (68.3% inhibition dark, 67.2% inhibition SSR) as expected and observed in previous experiments with *C. elegans* (Chapters 6.2.1 and 6.2.2). There is a highly significant change in inhibition when working under SSR with nTiO_2 . Irradiation seems to activate the toxic impact of nTiO_2 from 14.1% up to 48.9% inhibition. The small but significant increase in inhibition regarding the combination of nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} (from 68.3 to 77.2%) under SSR can therefore be explained through the additive toxicity of nTiO_2 and Cd^{2+} .

Figure 6.11: Cell Viability Assay with CHO-K1 cells, exposing them to 40 mg/L nTiO_2 , 1 mg/L Cd^{2+} and their combination under dark and irradiated conditions (30 minutes of SSR) with $n=3$.

Table 6.2: Adjusted *P* values of Bonferroni's multiple comparison of the different exposure combinations under dark and irradiated conditions shown in Figure 6.11.

	Dark	SSR
Cd^{2+} (1 mg/L) vs. nTiO_2 (40 mg/L)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
nTiO_2 (40 mg/L) + Cd^{2+} (1 mg/L) vs. nTiO_2 (40 mg/L)	< 0.0001	< 0.0001
nTiO_2 (40 mg/L) + Cd^{2+} (1 mg/L) vs. Cd^{2+} (1 mg/L)	> 0.9999	0.0049

6.3 Discussion

6.3.1 The role of free intracellular calcium

The measurement of free intracellular calcium with rhodamine is a first attempt to explain the toxicity of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ towards *C. elegans*. Calcium-gated ion channels play a relevant role in the self-defence mechanisms of living cells, therefore the impact of different chemicals can be evaluated by measuring the calcium intensity (Kawaii et al., 1993, Berridge et al., 2000, Cerella et al., 2010).

Single nTiO₂ has no direct impact on intracellular Ca²⁺ levels in this thesis, neither under dark nor illuminated conditions, whereby there is a slight drop in intensity directly after irradiation. Studies show that nTiO₂ can increase intracellular Ca²⁺ levels by acting on calcium-related channel proteins or downregulate the activity of Ca²⁺-ATPase. But this effect was only observed after long-term exposure to high concentrated nTiO₂-solutions on rats (Yang et al., 2023). The nanoparticles are also known to induce the production of ROS under irradiated conditions, which could lead indirectly to a disturbance in Ca²⁺ homeostasis (Delamere et al., 1991, Zaidi et al., 2009, Zaidi and Michaelis, 1999). This may explain the slight drop directly after SSR (Figure 6.4 and Figure 6.5). Another possible mode of action is an nTiO₂-induced cellular Ca²⁺ overload by acting on calcium-related channel proteins, but this was only reported on mucin in GhaGo-K1 epithelial cells (Chen et al., 2011) and histamine in RBL-2H3 mast cells (Chen et al., 2012). There are no references regarding the effect on calcium homeostasis in *C. elegans*.

Since over 30 years, Cd²⁺ is known to induce a variety of toxicity symptoms in animals and humans as well as in the environment (Asvadi and Hayes, 1978, Lee, 1972, Nriagu, 1981). Especially in the early stages after exposure, which include up to 16 hours, an enhancement in lipid peroxidation (Sato et al., 1983, Stacey and Klaassen, 1981) and impairment of antioxidative defence mechanisms like an increase in glutathione levels were measured which indicate the first steps of cell defence (Eaton et al., 1980, Siegers et al., 1986, Singhal et al., 1987).

The measured increase of Ca²⁺ in all experiments implies the activation of the self-defence mechanism of the cells in *C. elegans* towards Cd²⁺ (Kiss and Osipenko, 1994, Gupta et al., 1991). This effect occurs independently of the irradiation, as Cd²⁺ ions are not photocatalytic active and are therefore not activated first, unlike nTiO₂.

Molecular mode of action

Both the combinations of nTiO₂ + Cd²⁺ and NS8593 + nTiO₂ lead to a decrease in intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration during the first experiments. This indicates that TRPM-like ion channel *Gon-2* is affected by the mixture of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺. The ion channel is blocked, and the self-defence mechanisms are downregulated, followed by a toxic impact of Cd²⁺. The egg production of *C. elegans* is disturbed, and it comes to the observed reproduction inhibition of 80% (Samet, 2017b).

But after repeating all the experiments with rhodamine for five times, the first results could not be reproduced. There is a measurable effect, but the outcomes differ substantially from each other. Therefore, the mode of action should be described as unspecific. All the substances Cd²⁺, La³⁺, Hep and NS8593 seem to cause damage in calcium signalling and lead to an increased toxicity. But they all target different receptors: La³⁺ blocks TRPM3-like GTL-1, Hep is an antagonist of IP₃-receptor ITR-1 and NS8593 is specific for TRPM7-like GON-2 (Chubanov and Gudermann, 2020, Saleem et al., 2014, Xiao and Xu, 2009). This indicates a different, more complex mode of action when the nTiO₂- Cd²⁺-agglomerates enter the intestine of *C. elegans*. The experimental results exclude a specific receptor and lead to the assumption that the properties of nTiO₂ such as photocatalytic activity play a more potent role.

6.3.2 Membrane integrity

The experiments show that the membrane integrity of *C. elegans* is only influenced by irradiated nTiO₂ in combination with Cd²⁺ ions. This marks a first step towards the clarification of the mode of action. The results are supported by experiments of Wang et al. (2021): They observed a damage in the cell structure of the green algae *Scenedesmus obliquus* when adding a mixture of nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺ with a ratio of 4:1 under a 12:12 hour light: dark cycle. The toxicity mode is described as partially additive and synergistic, with nTiO₂ as a carrier of Cd²⁺ ions and enhancing the amount of Cd²⁺ ions entering the algae cell. They showed a mechanical and oxidative damage of the algae cell membrane, which is comparable to the results gained with *C. elegans*, but the different irradiation times should be considered (30 minutes in *C. elegans*, 12 hours for *S. obliquus*).

6.3.3 Cell viability assay

The results of the cell viability assay lead to the conclusion that mammalian cell lines such as CHO-K1 have a basic reaction to photocatalytic-activated nTiO₂. The effect is enhanced additively by the cell toxic cadmium, but the main effect lies with the photocatalytic activity of nTiO₂. CHO-K1 cells showed less sensitivity to nTiO₂ than other cell lines, such as human lung carcinoma cells, but the cellular response is described *via* a cell-cycle arrest at a pre-development stage (Moe et al., 2013). The photocatalytic activity of nTiO₂ causes a formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) under ultraviolet radiation A (UVA) exposure at Human HaCaT keratinocytes, a transformed epidermal human cell line, which releases lactate dehydrogenase (LDH). This enzyme causes a membrane damage in the cells, which is both concentration- and dose-dependent of the nanoparticle (Yin et al., 2012). The peroxidation of polyunsaturated lipids in the plasma membrane could explain the observed phototoxicity (Yin et al., 2009). Yin et al. (2012) proposed a mechanism of TiO₂ nanoparticle-induced free radicals and lipid-protein peroxidation leading to cell damage (Figure 6.12): The irradiation with UVA leads to electron-hole pairs in the nanoparticle, which causes an energy transfer to molecular oxygen and can form single oxygen (¹O₂) or hydroxyl radicals (\cdot OH). In the presence of a lipid or protein, these reactive oxygen species indicate peroxidation and therefore cell damage.

Figure 6.12: Proposed mechanism of TiO₂ nanoparticle-induced free radicals and lipid-protein peroxidation leading to cell damage, adapted from Yin et al. (2012).

Compared to the results with *C. elegans*, a synergistic mode of action seems to be excludable for CHO-K1 cells, but rather effect additively. But it is also possible that the toxicity towards cadmium ions is simply already so high, that any additional enhancement by nTiO₂ or SSR hardly matters any more. Experiments by Yang et al.

Molecular mode of action

(2004) observed a dose-dependent reduction of cell proliferation when more than 0.4 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ of Cd^{2+} was given to CHO-K1 cells.

7 Conclusion and Outlook

This thesis was aimed to answer these four questions:

- How do nanoparticles react with contaminants in the environment, especially in the aqueous milieu, under UV radiation?
- Are there changes in the chemical behaviour with direct sunlight?
- How do small invertebrates react to the particles, which are small enough to be ingested by them?
- Are there risk assessments and studies that evaluate the impact?

The experiments concerning the characterisation of the nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-agglomerates show that an adsorption of cadmium ions by nTiO₂ takes place, but it is only attached *via* ionic bonds. It is pH-dependent and influenced by simulated solar radiation regarding the agglomeration size. The adsorption process is described by a chemisorption and includes acid-base behaviour of nTiO₂ towards Cd²⁺ resulting in an increase in particle size due to thicker double layers at higher Cd²⁺ concentrations.

The measurement of the intracellular calcium concentration (Chapter 6.3.1) confirms the high toxicity of Cd²⁺ to *C. elegans*. But it does not prove the hypothesis of a defined mode of action regarding the involvement of a specific Ca²⁺ receptor when the nematodes are exposed to the combination of nTiO₂, Cd²⁺ and SSR. The results are not reproducible in constant matter, which leads to the conclusion that the mode of action is rather unspecific. The following hypothesis focusses on the integrity of the intestinal cell membrane, which is verifiably disturbed by nTiO₂ and Cd²⁺.

The measurements of the elemental composition (Chapter 5.2.3) show the pH-dependency: at pH 7, Cd²⁺ is adsorbed by nTiO₂ (Figure 7.1, step A) and ingested by *C. elegans*, while during the beginning passage into the intestine, irradiation occurs through the transparent roundworm (Figure 7.1, step B) and trigger the photoactivation of nTiO₂. The adsorbed cadmium ions enhance that photocatalytic activity through the principle of hole trapping, and the agglomerated particles leads to a membrane rupture with Cd²⁺ ions entering the cell (Figure 7.1, step C). This effect is supported by the observations focussing on the membrane integrity (Chapter 6.2.2): The main absorption of propidium iodide is measured in the pharynx and upper part of the intestine of *C.*

Conclusion and Outlook

elegans, where the pH value is between 7 and 5.5 (Chauhan et al., 2013), while it descends to pH 4 in the subsequent course of the intestine where the cadmium ions are already detached from nTiO₂ and cause no further effect (Figure 7.1, step D).

Figure 7.1: Overview of the suggested mode of action with the different stages of reaction A to D.

Concluding from the results of the experiments described in this thesis, the mode of action is proposed as followed: nTiO₂, dissolved in M9 medium, adsorb an amount of cadmium ions, depending on their concentration. They form agglomerates of approximately 2 μm , which are ingested by *C. elegans*. Their transparency allows irradiation to activate the photocatalytic activity of nTiO₂, which is also enhanced by Cd²⁺. The photoactivation enables the interaction of the nTiO₂-Cd²⁺-agglomerates with the membranes of cells of the upper gastrointestinal system, leading to a severe damage to the membrane integrity. The disturbance in the signalling system due to exiting ions such as Ca²⁺ through the damaged membrane lead to the observed increase in toxicity.

Only three of four questions could be answered with this work, a concrete risk assessment is still not possible. In order to prove the environmental importance, more

Conclusion and Outlook

experiments on realistic conditions are needed. It is decisive to check other biomolecules their behaviour, structure changes and reaction with nTiO₂.

One proposed mechanism is the emergence of CdO due to redox reactions (chapter 5.3.2). To prove that theory, samples could be collected and checked for the presence of CdO and how this could affect the environment.

Also, "hot topics" like climate change and its impact on pH values and bioactivity in soils and sediments should be addressed in further research. This thesis proves the importance of pH values and its effect on different agglomerates and particles, so the main question would be to evaluate a more diverse sample of anorganic and organic molecules which could interact with nTiO₂.

8 Bibliography

- 10872, I. 2010-06. Water quality — Determination of the toxic effect of sediment and soil samples on growth, fertility and reproduction of *Caenorhabditis elegans* (Nematoda).
- Adel, A. M., Ahmed, N. M., Diab, M. A. & Selim, M. M. 2016. The influence of TiO₂/CC core/shell pigments on the properties of paper sheets. *Powder Technology*, 291, 437-447.
- Ahmed, S. N. & Haider, W. 2018. Heterogeneous photocatalysis and its potential applications in water and wastewater treatment: a review. *Nanotechnology*, 29, 342001.
- Angelstorf, J. 2013. *Effekte von Titandioxidnanopartikeln auf den Nematoden Caenorhabditis elegans unter besonderer Berücksichtigung von UV-Strahlung*. Dissertation, Technische Universität Hamburg-Harburg.
- Angelstorf, J., Ahlf, W., von der Kammer, F. & Heise, S. 2014. Impact of particle size and light exposure on the effects of TiO₂ nanoparticles on *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 33, 2288-2296.
- Asvadi, S. & Hayes, J. A. 1978. Acute lung injury induced by cadmium aerosol. *American Journal of Pathology*, 90, 89-98.
- Balbi, T., Smerilli, A., Fabbri, R., Ciacci, C., Montagna, M., Grasselli, E., Brunelli, A., Pojana, G., Marcomini, A., Gallo, G. & Canesi, L. 2014. Co-exposure to n-TiO₂ and Cd²⁺ results in interactive effects on biomarker responses but not in increased toxicity in the marine bivalve *M. galloprovincialis*. *Science of the Total Environment*, 493, 355-64.
- Bameri, L., Sourinejad, I., Ghasemi, Z. & Fazelian, N. 2022. Toxicity of TiO₂ nanoparticles to the marine microalga *Chaetoceros muelleri* Lemmermann, 1898 under long-term exposure. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29, 30427-30440.
- Baumeister, R. 2005. Der Wurm in uns - *C. elegans* Forschung in Deutschland. *BIOspektrum*, 1, 95-96.
- Baur, W. 1955. Atomabstände und Bindungswinkel im Rutil. *Naturwissenschaften*, 42, 295-296.
- Becker, K., Schroecksnadel, S., Geisler, S., Carriere, M., Gostner, J. M., Schennach, H., Herlin, N. & Fuchs, D. 2014. TiO₂ nanoparticles and bulk material stimulate human peripheral blood mononuclear cells. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 65, 63-9.
- Bennat, C. & Müller-Goymann, C. C. 2000. Skin penetration and stabilization of formulations containing microfine titanium dioxide as physical UV filter. *International Journal of Cosmetic Science*, 22, 271-283.
- Berridge, M. J., Lipp, P. & Bootman, M. D. 2000. The versatility and universality of calcium signalling. *Nature Reviews. Molecular Cell Biology*, 1, 11-21.
- Bhagyaraj, S. M., Oluwafemi, O. S., Kalarikkal, N. & Thomas, S. 2018. *Synthesis of Inorganic Nanomaterials*, Woodhead Publishing.
- Carbajo, J., Tolosana-Moranchel, A., Casas, J. A., Faraldos, M. & Bahamonde, A. 2018. Analysis of photoefficiency in TiO₂ aqueous suspensions: Effect of titania hydrodynamic particle size and catalyst loading on their optical properties. *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 221, 1-8.
- Carneiro, J. O., Teixeira, V., Portinha, A., Magalhães, A., Coutinho, P., Tavares, C. J. & Newton, R. 2007. Iron-doped photocatalytic TiO₂ sputtered coatings on plastics for self-cleaning applications. *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, 138, 144-150.
- Cerella, C., Diederich, M. & Ghibelli, L. 2010. The dual role of calcium as messenger and stressor in cell damage, death, and survival. *International Journal of Cell Biology*, 2010, 546163.
- Chauhan, V. M., Orsi, G., Brown, A., Pritchard, D. I. & Aylott, J. 2013. Mapping the Pharyngeal and Intestinal pH of *Caenorhabditis elegans* and Real-Time Luminal pH Oscillations Using Extended Dynamic Range pH-Sensitive Nanosensors. *ACS Nano*, 7, 5577-5587.
- Chen, E. Y., Garnica, M., Wang, Y. C., Chen, C. S. & Chin, W. C. 2011. Mucin secretion induced by titanium dioxide nanoparticles. *PLoS One*, 6, e16198.

Bibliography

- Chen, E. Y., Garnica, M., Wang, Y. C., Mintz, A. J., Chen, C. S. & Chin, W. C. 2012. A mixture of anatase and rutile TiO₂ nanoparticles induces histamine secretion in mast cells. *Part Fibre Toxicol*, 9, 2.
- Chislock, M. F., Doster, E., Zitomer, R. A. & Wilson, A. E. 2013. Eutrophication: Causes, Consequences, and Controls in Aquatic Ecosystems. *Nature Education Knowledge*, 4.
- Chubanov, V. & Gudermann, T. 2020. Mapping TRPM7 Function by NS8593. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21.
- Church, D. L. & Lambie, E. J. 2003. The Promotion of Gonadal Cell Divisions by the *Caenorhabditis elegans* TRPM Cation Channel GON-2 is antagonized by GEM-4 Copine. *Genetics*, 165, 563-574.
- Delamere, N. A., Paterson, C. A., Borchmann, D., King, K. L. & Cawood, S. A. 1991. Calcium transport, Ca²⁺-ATPase, and lipid order in rabbit ocular lens membranes. *American Journal of Physiology-Cell Physiology*, 260, 731-737.
- Deng, R., Lin, D., Zhu, L., Majumdar, S., White, J. C., Gardea-Torresdey, J. L. & Xing, B. 2017. Nanoparticle interactions with co-existing contaminants: joint toxicity, bioaccumulation and risk. *Nanotoxicology*, 11, 591-612.
- Denton, G. R. W. & Burdon-Jones, C. 1986. Environmental Effects on Toxicity of Heavy Metals to Two Species of Tropical Marine Fish from Northern Australia. *Chemistry and Ecology*, 2, 233-249.
- Derjaguin, B. & Landau, L. 1941. Theory of the stability of strongly charged lyophobic sols and of the adhesion of strongly charged particles in solutions of electrolytes. *Acta Physicochimica U.R.S.S.*, 14, 633-663.
- Duijnsveld, W. H. M., Godbersen, L., Dilling, J., Gäbler, H.-E., Utermann, J., Klump, G. & Scheeder, G. 2008. Ermittlung flächenrepräsentativer Hintergrundkonzentrationen prioritärer Schadstoffe im Bodensickerwasser. In: ROHSTOFFE), F. I. F. G. A. N. R. B. F. G. U. (ed.). Hanover.
- Eaton, D. L., Stacey, N. H., Wong, K. L. & Klaassen, C. D. 1980. Dose response effects of various metal ions on rat liver metallothionein, glutathione, heme oxygenase and cytochrome P-450. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 55, 393-402.
- Engates, K. E. & Shipley, H. J. 2011. Adsorption of Pb, Cd, Cu, Zn, and Ni to titanium dioxide nanoparticles: effect of particle size, solid concentration, and exhaustion. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 18, 386-95.
- Evonik Operations GmbH 2021. Produktinformation AEROXIDE TiO₂ P 25.
- Gao, Y., Wahi, R., Kan, A. T., Falkner, J. C., Colvin, V. L. & Tomson, M. B. 2004. Adsorption of Cadmium on Anatase Nanoparticles - Effect of Crystal Size and pH. *Langmuir*, 20, 9585-9593.
- Gea, M., Bonetta, S., Iannarelli, L., Giovannozzi, A. M., Maurino, V., Bonetta, S., Hodoroaba, V.-D.-., Armato, C., Rossi, A. M. & Schilirò, T. 2019. Shape-engineered titanium dioxide nanoparticles (TiO₂-NPs): cytotoxicity and genotoxicity in bronchial epithelial cells. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 127, 89-100.
- Goering, P. L., Waalkes, M. P. & Klaassen, C. D. 1994. *Toxicology of Cadmium*, New York, Springer-Verlag.
- Gottschalk, F., Lassen, C., Kjoelholt, J., Christensen, F. & Nowack, B. 2015. Modeling Flows and Concentrations of Nine Engineered Nanomaterials in the Danish Environment. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 12, 5581-5602.
- Gunstone, T., Cornelisse, T., Klein, K., Dubey, A. & Donley, N. 2021. Pesticides and Soil Invertebrates: A Hazard Assessment. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 9.
- Gupta, S., Athar, M., Behari, J. R. & Srivastava, R. C. 1991. Cadmium-mediated Induction of Cellular Defence Mechanism: a Novel Example for the Development of Adaptive Response against a Toxicant. *Industrial Health*, 29, 1-9.

Bibliography

- Guzmán, D. K. A., Taylor, M. R. & Banfield, J. F. 2006. Environmental risks of nanotechnology: National Nanotechnology Initiative Funding, 2000-2004. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 40, 1401-1407.
- Handy, R. D., Cornelis, G., Fernandes, T., Tsyusko, O., Decho, A., Sabo-Attwood, T., Metcalfe, C., Steevens, J. A., Klaine, S. J., Koelmans, A. A. & Horne, N. 2012. Ecotoxicity test methods for engineered nanomaterials: practical experiences and recommendations from the bench. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 31, 15-31.
- Haq, S., Rehman, W. & Waseem, M. 2018. Adsorption Efficiency of Anatase TiO₂ Nanoparticles Against Cadmium Ions. *Journal of Inorganic and Organometallic Polymers and Materials*, 29, 651-658.
- Hartmann, N. B. & Baun, A. 2010. The nano cocktail: ecotoxicological effects of engineered nanoparticles in chemical mixtures. *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, 6, 311-14.
- Hartmann, N. B., Legros, S., Von der Kammer, F., Hofmann, T. & Baun, A. 2012. The potential of TiO₂ nanoparticles as carriers for cadmium uptake in *Lumbricus variegatus* and *Daphnia magna*. *Aquatic Toxicology*, 118-119, 1-8.
- Heise, S., Krüger, F., Förstner, U., Baborowski, M., Götz, R. & Stachel, B. 2007. Bewertung der Risiken durch Feststoffgebundene Schadstoffe im Elbeinzugsgebiet. Im Auftrag der Flussgebietsgemeinschaft Elbe und Hamburg Port Authority, erstellt vom Beratungszentrum für integriertes Sedimentmanagement (BIS/TuTech) an der TU Hamburg-Harburg. Hamburg.
- Hope, I. A. 1999. *Background on Caenorhabditis elegans*, Oxford University Press.
- Höss, S., Schlottmann, K. & Traunspurger, W. 2011. Toxicity of ingested cadmium to the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 45, 10219-25.
- Huang, Z., Liu, C., Zhao, X., Dong, J. & Zheng, B. 2020. Risk assessment of heavy metals in the surface sediment at the drinking water source of the Xiangjiang River in South China. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 32.
- Hunklinger, S. 2017. *Festkörperphysik*, Oldenburg, Berlin, Boston, De Gruyter.
- Invitrogen 2006. Propidium Iodide Nucleic Acid Stain Manual MP 01304. *Molecular probes*.
- Jaroenworarluck, A., Sunsaneeyametha, W., Kosachan, N. & Stevens, R. 2006. Characteristics of silica-coated TiO₂ and its UV absorption for sunscreen cosmetic applications. *Surface and Interface Analysis*, 38, 473-477.
- Ji, Y., Zhou, Y., Ma, C., Feng, Y., Hao, Y., Rui, Y., Wu, W., Gui, X., Le, V. N., Han, Y., Wang, Y., Xing, B., Liu, L. & Cao, W. 2017. Jointed toxicity of TiO₂ NPs and Cd to rice seedlings: NPs alleviated Cd toxicity and Cd promoted NPs uptake. *Plant Physiol Biochem*, 110, 82-93.
- Jiang, J., Oberdörster, G. & Biswas, P. 2008. Characterization of size, surface charge, and agglomeration state of nanoparticle dispersions for toxicological studies. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 11, 77-89.
- Jovanović, B. 2015. Review of titanium dioxide nanoparticle phototoxicity: Developing a phototoxicity ratio to correct the endpoint values of toxicity tests. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 34, 1070-1077.
- Kahru, A. & Dubourguier, H. C. 2010. From ecotoxicology to nanoecotoxicology. *Toxicology*, 269, 105-19.
- Karlsson, M. C. F., Álvarez-Asencio, R., Bordes, R., Larsson, A., Taylor, P. & Steenari, B.-M. 2018. Characterization of paint formulated using secondary TiO₂ pigments recovered from waste paint. *Journal of Coatings Technology and Research*, 16, 607-614.
- Kawai, S., Yoshizawa, Y. & Mizutani, J. 1993. Measurement of Intracellular Ionized Calcium in a Free-living Soil Nematode, *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Bioscience, Biotechnology, and Biochemistry*, 57, 1115-8.

Bibliography

- Kayser, A. 2020. Parameterblatt Cadmium. In: NIEDERSÄCHSISCHER LANDESBETRIEB FÜR WASSERWIRTSCHAFT, K.-U. N. (ed.) *Grundwasserbericht Niedersachsen*. Norden, Germany.
- Kelly, C. A., Farzad, F., Thompson, D. W., Stipkala, J. M. & Meyer, G. J. 1999. Cation-Controlled Interfacial Charge Injection in Sensitized Nanocrystalline TiO₂. *Langmuir*, 15, 7047 - 7054.
- Kiss, T. & Osipenko, O. N. 1994. Toxic effects of heavy metals on ionic channels. *Pharmacological Reviews*, 46, 245–267.
- Klaine, S. J., Alvarez, P. J. J., Batley, G. B., Fernandes, T. F., Handy, R. D., Lyon, D. Y., Mahendra, S., McLaughlin, M. J. & Lead, J. R. 2008. Nanomaterials in the environment: Behavior, fate, bioavailability, and effects. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 27, 1825-1851.
- Klaine, S. J., Koelmans, A. A., Horne, N., Carley, S., Handy, R. D., Kapustka, L., Nowack, B. & von der Kammer, F. 2012. Paradigms to assess the environmental impact of manufactured nanomaterials. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 31, 3-14.
- Krischner, H. & Koppelhuber-Bitschnau, B. 1994. *Röntgenstrukturanalyse und Rietveldmethode*, Wiesbaden, Springer Fachmedien.
- Kubier, A., Wilkin, R. T. & Pichler, T. 2019. Cadmium in soils and groundwater: A review. *Applied Geochemistry*, 108, 1-16.
- Kuempel, E. D., Tran, C. L., Castranova, V. & Bailer, A. J. 2006. Lung dosimetry and risk assessment of nanoparticles: evaluating and extending current models in rats and humans. *Inhal Toxicol*, 18, 717-24.
- Kumar, V., Wanchoo, R. K. & Toor, A. P. 2021. Sequential removal and recovery of cadmium ions (Cd²⁺) using photocatalysis and reduction crystallization from the aqueous phase. *Reaction Chemistry & Engineering*, 6, 1677-1687.
- Lambie, E. J., Bruce, R. D., 3rd, Zielich, J. & Yuen, S. N. 2015. Novel Alleles of *gon-2*, a *C. elegans* Ortholog of Mammalian TRPM6 and TRPM7, Obtained by Genetic Reversion Screens. *PLoS One*, 10, e0143445.
- Langmuir, I. 1916. The constitution and fundamental properties of solids and liquids. Part I. Solids. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 38, 2221-2295.
- Lee, D. H. K. 1972. *Metallic contaminants and Human Health*, New York, Academic Press.
- Lewicka, Z. A., Benedetto, A. F., Benoit, D. N., Yu, W. W., Fortner, J. D. & Colvin, V. L. 2011. The structure, composition, and dimensions of TiO₂ and ZnO nanomaterials in commercial sunscreens. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 13, 3607-3617.
- Lewis, N. S. 1998. Progress in Understanding Electron-Transfer Reactions at Semiconductor/Liquid Interfaces. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 102, 4843 - 4855.
- Li, R., Li, T. & Zhou, Q. 2020. Impact of Titanium Dioxide (TiO₂) Modification on Its Application to Pollution Treatment—A Review. *Catalysts*, 10, 804.
- Lindberg, H. K., Falck, G. C., Catalan, J., Koivisto, A. J., Suhonen, S., Jarventaus, H., Rossi, E. M., Nykasenoja, H., Peltonen, Y., Moreno, C., Alenius, H., Tuomi, T., Savolainen, K. M. & Norppa, H. 2012. Genotoxicity of inhaled nanosized TiO₂ in mice. *Mutat Res*, 745, 58-64.
- Lorenz, C., von Pelchrzim, F. & Schroeder, R. 2006. Genomic systematic evolution of ligands by exponential enrichment (Genomic SELEX) for the identification of protein-binding RNAs independent of their expression levels. *Nature Protocols*, 1, 2204-12.
- Ma-Hock, L., Burkhardt, S., Strauss, V., Gamer, A. O., Wiench, K., van Ravenzwaay, B. & Landsiedel, R. 2009. Development of a short-term inhalation test in the rat using nano-titanium dioxide as a model substance. *Inhal Toxicol*, 21, 102-18.
- Ma, T., Wang, M., Gong, S. & Tian, B. 2017. Impacts of Sediment Organic Matter Content and pH on Ecotoxicity of Coexposure of TiO₂ Nanoparticles and Cadmium to Freshwater Snails *Bellamya aeruginosa*. *Archives of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 72, 153-165.
- Macherauch, E. & Zoch, H.-W. 2011. *Praktikum in Werkstoffkunde*, Vieweg+Teubner.

Bibliography

- Malvern Dynamic Light Scattering: An Introduction in 30 Minutes. *DLS Technical Note MRK656-01*, 1-8.
- Maness, P.-C., Smolinski, S., Blake, D. M., Huang, Z., Wolfrum, E. J. & Jacoby, W. A. 1999. Bactericidal Activity of Photocatalytic TiO₂ Reaction: toward an Understanding of Its Killing Mechanism. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 65, 4094-4098.
- Martelli, A., Rousselet, E., Dycke, C., Bouron, A. & Moulis, J. M. 2006. Cadmium toxicity in animal cells by interference with essential metals. *Biochimie*, 88, 1807-14.
- Miyoshi, A., Kato, K., Yokoi, T., Wiesfeld, J. J., Nakajima, K., Yamakara, A. & Maeda, K. 2020. Nano vs. bulk rutile TiO₂:N,F in Z-scheme overall water splitting under visible light. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, 8, 11996-12002.
- Moe, B., Gabos, S. & Li, X. F. 2013. Real-time cell-microelectronic sensing of nanoparticle-induced cytotoxic effects. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 789, 83-90.
- Molecular Probes 2014. Rhod-3 Calcium Imaging Kit. *molecular probes by life technologies*, MAN0001973 MP10145.
- Monteiro-Riviere, N. A., Wiench, K., Landsiedel, R., Schulte, S., Inman, A. O. & Riviere, J. E. 2011. Safety evaluation of sunscreen formulations containing titanium dioxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles in UVB sunburned skin: an in vitro and in vivo study. *Toxicol Sci*, 123, 264-80.
- Mühlfeld, C., Geiser, M., Kapp, N., Gehr, P. & Rothen-Rutishauser, B. 2007. Re-evaluation of pulmonary titanium dioxide nanoparticle distribution using the "relative deposition index": Evidence for clearance through microvasculature. *Part Fibre Toxicol*, 4, 7.
- Müller, G. 1977. Schadstoff-Untersuchungen an datierten Sedimentkernen aus dem Bodensee. II. Historische Entwicklung von Schwermetallen - Beziehung zur Entwicklung polycyclischer aromatischer Kohlenwasserstoffe. *Naturforschung*, 32c, 913-919.
- Naasz, S., Altenburger, R. & Kuhnel, D. 2018. Environmental mixtures of nanomaterials and chemicals: The Trojan-horse phenomenon and its relevance for ecotoxicity. *Science of the Total Environment*, 635, 1170-1181.
- Nam, Y., Lim, J. H., Ko, K. C. & Lee, J. Y. 2019. Photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ nanoparticles: a theoretical aspect. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, 7, 13833-13859.
- Naqvi, F. K., Anwar, K. & Beg, S. 2021. Ex Situ Method for Photoreduction of the Cadmium Ion from Terbium-Loaded Bismuth Vanadium Oxide. *ACS Omega*, 6, 31716-31726.
- Nia, M. H., Rezaei-Tavirani, M., Nikoofar, A. R., Masoumi, H., Nasr, R., Hasanzadeh, H., Jadidi, M. & Shadnush, M. 2015. Stabilizing and dispersing methods of TiO₂ nanoparticles in biological studies. *Journal of Paramedical Sciences*, 6, 96-105.
- Nowack, B., Ranville, J. F., Diamond, S., Gallego-Urrea, J. A., Metcalfe, C., Rose, J., Horne, N., Koelmans, A. A. & Klaine, S. J. 2012. Potential scenarios for nanomaterial release and subsequent alteration in the environment. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 31, 50-9.
- Nriagu, J. O. 1981. *Cadmium in the environment*, New York, Wiley Interscience.
- Ohtani, B., Prieto-Mahaney, O. O., Li, D. & Abe, R. 2010. What is Degussa (Evonik) P25? Crystalline composition analysis, reconstruction from isolated pure particles and photocatalytic activity test. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, 216, 179-182.
- Parker, R. L. 1924. Zur Kristallstruktur von Anatas und Rutil. (II. Teil. Die Anatasstruktur). *Zeitschrift für Kristallographie*, 59, 1-54.
- Petersen, E. J. & Henry, T. B. 2012. Methodological considerations for testing the ecotoxicity of carbon nanotubes and fullerenes: review. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 31, 60-72.
- Priester, J. H., Ge, Y., Chang, V., Stoimenov, P. K., Schimmel, J. P., Stucky, G. D. & Holden, P. A. 2013. Assessing interactions of hydrophilic nanoscale TiO₂ with soil water. *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 15.
- Promega 2017. CellTiter-Fluor™ Cell Viability Assay. TB371.

Bibliography

- Rajh, T., Nedeljkovic, J. M., Chen, L. X., Poluektov, O. & Thurnauer, M. C. 1999. Improving Optical and Charge Separation Properties of Nanocrystalline TiO₂ by Surface Modification with Vitamin C. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 103, 3515 - 3519.
- Ren, W., Yan, Y., Zeng, L., Shi, Z., Gong, A., Schaaf, P., Wang, D., Zhao, J., Zou, B., Yu, H., Chen, G., Brown, E. M. & Wu, A. 2015. A Near Infrared Light Triggered Hydrogenated Black TiO₂ for Cancer Photothermal Therapy. *Advanced Healthcare Materials*, 4, 1526-36.
- Robichaud, C. O., Uyar, A. E., Darby, M. R., Zucker, L. G. & Wiesner, M. R. 2009. Estimates of Upper Bounds and Trends in Nano-TiO₂ Production As a Basis for Exposure Assessment. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 43, 4227-4233.
- Roh, J.-Y., Lee, J. & Choi, J. 2006. Assessment of stress-related gene expression in the heavy metal-exposed nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*: a potential biomarker for metal-induced toxicity monitoring and environmental risk assessment. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 25, 2946-2956.
- Rossini, G. D. B. & Ronco, A. E. 1996. Acute Toxicity Bioassay Using *Daphnia obtusa* as a Test Organism. *Environmental Toxicology and Water Quality*, 11, 255-258.
- Sadrieh, N., Wokovich, A. M., Gopee, N. V., Zheng, J., Haines, D., Parmiter, D., Siitonen, P. H., Cozart, C. R., Patri, A. K., McNeil, S. E., Howard, P. C., Doub, W. H. & Buhse, L. F. 2010. Lack of significant dermal penetration of titanium dioxide from sunscreen formulations containing nano- and submicron-size TiO₂ particles. *Toxicol Sci*, 115, 156-66.
- Saleem, H., Tovey, S. C., Molinski, T. F. & Taylor, C. W. 2014. Interactions of antagonists with subtypes of inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate (IP₃) receptor. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 171, 3298-312.
- Samet, K. Abstract SETAC Europe Annual Meeting 2017: Investigation on the mode of action of n-TiO₂ with co-exposed Cd in the nematode test using *Caenorhabditis elegans*. In: SETAC, ed. SETAC Europe, 2017a Brussels. SETAC.
- Samet, K. 2017b. *Investigation of the mode of action when co-exposing the nematode Caenorhabditis elegans to heavy metals and TiO₂ nanoparticles*. PhD, University of the West of Scotland.
- Sato, M., Yamanobe, K. & Nagai Y. , L. S. 1983. Sex related differences in cadmium induced lipid peroxidation in the rat. *Life Science*, 903-908.
- Schaumann, G. E., Philippe, A., Bundschuh, M., Metreveli, G., Klitzke, S., Rakcheev, D., Grun, A., Kumahor, S. K., Kuhn, M., Baumann, T., Lang, F., Manz, W., Schulz, R. & Vogel, H. J. 2015. Understanding the fate and biological effects of Ag- and TiO₂-nanoparticles in the environment: The quest for advanced analytics and interdisciplinary concepts. *Science of the Total Environment*, 535, 3-19.
- Schmid, O., Moller, W., Semmler-Behnke, M., Ferron, G. A., Karg, E., Lipka, J., Schulz, H., Kreyling, W. G. & Stoeger, T. 2009. Dosimetry and toxicology of inhaled ultrafine particles. *Biomarkers*, 14 Suppl 1, 67-73.
- Schütze, G., Becker, R., Dämmgen, U., Nagel, H.-D., Schlutow, A. & Weigel, H.-J. 2003. Risikoabschätzung der Cadmium-Belastung für mensch und Umwelt infolge der Anwendung von cadmiumhaltigen Düngemitteln. *Landbauforschung Völkenrode* 2/3, 53, 63-170.
- Scuri, M., Chen, B. T., Castranova, V., Reynolds, J. S., Johnson, V. J., Samsell, L., Walton, C. & Piedimonte, G. 2010. Effects of titanium dioxide nanoparticle exposure on neuroimmune responses in rat airways. *J Toxicol Environ Health A*, 73, 1353-69.
- Sengul, A. B. & Asmatulu, E. 2020. Toxicity of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles: a review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 18, 1659-1683.
- Serpone, N. & Emeline, A. V. 2002. Suggested terms and definitions in photocatalysis and radiocatalysis. *International Journal of Photoenergy*, 4, 91-141.
- Seyforth, J. A. 2015. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM): An Introduction to the use of SEM for characterising the Surface Topology and Composition of Matter with Further Applications *Experimental Techniques In Condensed Matter Physics*.

Bibliography

- Shakeel, M., Jabeen, F., Shabbir, S., Asghar, M. S., Khan, M. S. & Chaudhry, A. S. 2016. Toxicity of Nano-Titanium Dioxide (TiO₂-NP) Through Various Routes of Exposure: a Review. *Biol Trace Elem Res*, 172, 1-36.
- Shi, H., Magaye, R., Castranova, V. & Zhao, J. 2013. Titanium dioxide nanoparticles: a review of current toxicological data. *Particle and Fibre Toxicology*, 10.
- Siegers, C. P., Sharma, S. C. & Younes, M. 1986. Hepatotoxicity of metals in glutathione depleted mice. *Toxicology Letters*, 34, 185-91.
- Singhal, R. K., Anderson, M. E. & Meister, A. 1987. Glutathione, a first line of defence against cadmium toxicity. *FAESB Journal*, 1, 220-3.
- Smijs, T. G. & Pavel, S. 2011. Titanium dioxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles in sunscreens: focus on their safety and effectiveness. *Nanotechnology, Science and Applications*, 4, 95-112.
- Spurgeon, D. J., Jones, O. A., Dorne, J. L., Svendsen, C., Swain, S. & Sturzenbaum, S. R. 2010. Systems toxicology approaches for understanding the joint effects of environmental chemical mixtures. *Science of the Total Environment*, 408, 3725-34.
- Stacey, N. H. & Klaassen, C. D. 1981. Comparison of the effects of metals on cellular injury and lipid peroxidation in isolated rat hepatocytes. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health*, 7, 139-47.
- Stevanovic, A., Buttner, M., Zhang, Z. & Yates, J. T., Jr. 2012. Photoluminescence of TiO₂: effect of UV light and adsorbed molecules on surface band structure. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, 134, 324-32.
- Sun, T. Y., Gottschalk, F., Hungerbuhler, K. & Nowack, B. 2014. Comprehensive probabilistic modelling of environmental emissions of engineered nanomaterials. *Environmental Pollution*, 185, 69-76.
- Tan, L. Y., Huang, B., Xu, S., Wei, Z. B., Yang, L. Y. & Miao, A. J. 2017. Aggregation Reverses the Carrier Effects of TiO₂ Nanoparticles on Cadmium Accumulation in the Waterflea *Daphnia magna*. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 51, 932-939.
- Teramoto, T., Lambie, E. J. & Iwasaki, K. 2005. Differential regulation of TRPM channels governs electrolyte homeostasis in the *C. elegans* intestine. *Cell Metabolism*, 1, 343-54.
- Thévenod, F. 2009. Cadmium and cellular signaling cascades: To be or not to be? *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 238, 221-39.
- Traunspurger, W., Haitzer, M., Höss, S., Beier, S., Ahlf, W. & Steinberg, C. 1997. Ecotoxicological assessment of aquatic sediments with *Caenorhabditis elegans* (Nematoda) - a method for testing liquid medium and whole-sediment samples. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 16, 245-250.
- Traunspurger, W., Steinberg, C. & Bongers, T. 1995. Nematoden in der ökotoxikologischen Forschung. *Zeitschrift für Umweltchemie und Ökotoxikologie*, 7, 74-83.
- Van der Heever, J. A. & Grobbelaar, J. U. 1996. The Use of *Selenastrum capricornutum* Growth Potential as a Measure of Toxicity of a Few Selected Compounds. *Water SA*, 22, 183-191.
- van Oss, C. J. 2008. Chapter Three - The Extended DLVO Theory. *Interface Science and Technology*, 16, 31-48.
- van Ravenzwaay, B., Landsiedel, R., Fabian, E., Burkhardt, S., Strauss, V. & Ma-Hock, L. 2009. Comparing fate and effects of three particles of different surface properties: nano-TiO₂, pigmentary TiO₂ and quartz. *Toxicol Lett*, 186, 152-9.
- Vert, M., Doi, Y., Hellwich, K.-H., Hess, M., Hodge, P., Kubisa, P., Rinaudo, M. & Schué, F. 2012. Terminology for biorelated polymers and applications (IUPAC Recommendations 2012). *Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 84, 377-410.
- Virkutyte, J., Al-Abed, S. R. & Dionysiou, D. D. 2012. Depletion of the protective aluminum hydroxide coating in TiO₂-based sunscreens by swimming pool water ingredients. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 191, 95-103.

Bibliography

- Waalkes, M. 2003. Cadmium carcinogenesis. *Mutation Research/Fundamental and Molecular Mechanisms of Mutagenesis*, 533, 107-120.
- Walker, D. S., Ly, S., Gower, N. J. & Baylis, H. A. 2004. IRI-1, a LIN-15B homologue, interacts with inositol-1,4,5-triphosphate receptors and regulates gonadogenesis, defecation, and pharyngeal pumping in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Molecular Biology of the Cell*, 15, 3073-82.
- Wang, J., Dai, H., Nie, Y., Wang, M., Yang, Z., Cheng, L., Liu, Y., Chen, S., Zhao, G., Wu, L., Guang, S. & Xu, A. 2018. TiO₂ nanoparticles enhance bioaccumulation and toxicity of heavy metals in *Caenorhabditis elegans* via modification of local concentrations during the sedimentation process. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 162, 160-169.
- Wang, P., Zhao, L., Huang, Y., Qian, W., Zhu, X., Wang, Z. & Cai, Z. 2021. Combined toxicity of nano-TiO₂ and Cd²⁺ to *Scenedesmus obliquus*: Effects at different concentration ratios. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 418, 1-8.
- Ward, S. H. 1989. The Requirements for a Balanced Medium in Toxicological Experiments Using *Mysidopsis bahia* with Special Reference to Calcium Carbonate. In: COWGILL, U. M. & WILLIAMS, L. R. (eds.) *Aquatic Toxicology and Hazard Assessment*. Philadelphia, PA: ASTM STP 1027.
- Weir, A., Westerhoff, P., Fabricius, L., Hristovski, K. & von Goetz, N. 2012. Titanium dioxide nanoparticles in food and personal care products. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 46, 2242-50.
- WormAtlas, Altun, Z. F., Herndon, L. A., Wolkow, C. A., Crocker, C., Lints, R. & Hall, D. H. 2017. Available: <http://www.wormatlas.org>.
- Wu, J., Liu, W., Xue, C., Zhou, S., Lan, F., Bi, L., Xu, H., Yang, X. & Zeng, F. D. 2009. Toxicity and penetration of TiO₂ nanoparticles in hairless mice and porcine skin after subchronic dermal exposure. *Toxicol Lett*, 191, 1-8.
- Xiao, R. & Xu, X. Z. 2009. Function and regulation of TRP family channels in *C. elegans*. *Pflugers Arch*, 458, 851-60.
- Xie, J. & Hung, Y.-C. 2018. UV-A activated TiO₂ embedded biodegradable polymer film for antimicrobial food packaging application. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, 96, 307-314.
- Xie, X. & Gao, L. 2009. Effect of crystal structure on adsorption behaviors of nanosized TiO₂ for heavy-metal cations. *Current Applied Physics*, 9, 5185-5188.
- Yang, P. M., Chiu, S. J., Lin, K. A. & Lin, L. Y. 2004. Effect of cadmium on cell cycle progression in Chinese hamster ovary cells. *Chemico-Biological Interactions*, 149, 125-36.
- Yang, W. W., Li, Y., Miao, A. J. & Yang, L. Y. 2012a. Cd²⁺ toxicity as affected by bare TiO₂ nanoparticles and their bulk counterpart. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 85, 44-51.
- Yang, W. W., Miao, A. J. & Yang, L. Y. 2012b. Cd²⁺ Toxicity to a green alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* as influenced by its adsorption on TiO₂ engineered nanoparticles. *PLoS One*, 7, e32300.
- Yang, W. W., Wang, Y., Huang, B., Wang, N. X., Wei, Z. B., Luo, J., Miao, A. J. & Yang, L. Y. 2014. TiO₂ nanoparticles act as a carrier of Cd bioaccumulation in the ciliate *Tetrahymena thermophila*. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 48, 7568-75.
- Yang, Y., Javed, H., Zhang, D., Li, D., Kamath, R., McVey, K., Sra, K. & Alvarez, P. J. J. 2017. Merits and limitations of TiO₂-based photocatalytic pretreatment of soils impacted by crude oil for expediting bioremediation. *Frontiers of Chemical Science and Engineering*, 11, 387-394.
- Yang, Y., Zhao, Y., Wang, Q., Liu, M., Chang, H., Li, L., Meng, X., Deng, Y., Ling, C., Wang, K., Song, G. & Sui, X. 2023. Effects of nano-titanium dioxide on calcium homeostasis in vivo and in vitro: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Toxicol Mech Methods*, 33, 249-259.

Bibliography

- Yin, J. J., Lao, F., Fu, P. P., Wamer, W. G., Zhao, Y., Wang, P. C., Qiu, Y., Sun, B., Xing, G., Dong, J., Liang, X. J. & Chen, C. 2009. The scavenging of reactive oxygen species and the potential for cell protection by functionalized fullerene materials. *Biomaterials*, 30, 611-21.
- Yin, J. J., Liu, J., Ehrenshaft, M., Roberts, J. E., Fu, P. P., Mason, R. P. & Zhao, B. 2012. Phototoxicity of nano titanium dioxides in HaCaT keratinocytes--generation of reactive oxygen species and cell damage. *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology*, 263, 81-8.
- Zaidi, A., Fernandes, D., Bean, J. L. & Michaelis, M. L. 2009. Effects of paraquat-induced oxidative stress on the neuronal plasma membrane Ca(2+)-ATPase. *Free Radical Biology & Medicine*, 47, 1507-14.
- Zaidi, A. & Michaelis, M. L. 1999. Effects on reactive oxygen species on brain synaptic plasma membrane Ca²⁺-ATPase. *Free Radical Biology & Medicine*, 27, 810-821.
- Zeta-Meter, I. 2022. Zeta Potential: A Complete Course in 5 Minutes.
- Zhang, X., Sun, H., Zhang, Z., Niu, Q., Chen, Y. & Crittenden, J. C. 2007. Enhanced bioaccumulation of cadmium in carp in the presence of titanium dioxide nanoparticles. *Chemosphere*, 67, 160-6.

9 Annex

Table 9.1: Statistical analysis of the four different samples considering titanium

Bonferroni's Multiple Comparison Test	Significant? P < 0.05?	Summary
<i>Ti A vs Ti B</i>	No	ns
<i>Ti A vs Ti C</i>	No	ns
<i>Ti A vs Ti D</i>	No	ns
<i>Ti B vs Ti C</i>	No	ns
<i>Ti B vs Ti D</i>	No	ns
<i>Ti C vs Ti D</i>	No	ns

Table 9.2: Statistical analysis of the four different samples considering oxygen

Bonferroni's Multiple Comparison Test	Significant? P < 0,05?	Summary
<i>O A vs O B</i>	No	ns
<i>O A vs O C</i>	No	ns
<i>O A vs O D</i>	No	ns
<i>O B vs O C</i>	No	ns
<i>O B vs O D</i>	No	ns
<i>O C vs O D</i>	No	ns